

crescine

Deliverable D7.1 Personas dashboard: CineFlux MVP

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Technical references

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1 Table of Contents

1	Table of Contents	3
2	Document Change Log	6
2.1	Statement of Originality	8
2.2	Disclaimer	8
3	Executive Summary	9
4	Introduction	16
4.1	Rationale for deviations relative to the DoA	17
4.2	Technology readiness level (TRL) of the CineFlux MVP	18
4.3	What changed, and what remained aligned with the DoA intent	19
4.4	Prioritization, reproducibility and risk control	20
4.5	Schedule adjustment	21
4.6	Net effect on output value	21
4.7	Structure of the report	21
5	Background	24
5.1	Data-driven audience insights in audiovisual media	24
5.1.1	Traditional approaches to audience research in media studies	24
5.1.2	The datafication of audiences and rise of analytics	24
5.1.3	AI-powered tools to obtain audience insights	26
5.1.4	Dashboards and decision support for audience analytics	27
5.1.5	Data-driven audience insights	29
5.1.6	Implications of the state of the art for CineFlux’s design	31
5.2	Focus groups	33
5.2.1	Focus groups and reception studies	34
5.2.2	Focus groups at scale	37
5.3	From black-box profiles to nuanced AI insights	38
5.3.1	Explanatory dimensions for audience reception	40
5.3.2	Toward explainable, nuanced profiles with language models	42

5.4	Interpretive value of reviewer stance	45
5.4.1	Stance as evidence of meaning-making processes	45
5.4.2	Stance: audience segmentation, and value alignment	47
5.4.3	Stance markers in computational audience modelling	48
6	The data	51
6.1	The films sample	51
6.1.1	Data characterization and preprocessing	54
6.1.2	Collection of public-review data	54
6.1.3	The final public-review corpus	56
6.2	Focus-group data	59
6.2.1	Structure of the collected data	63
6.2.2	Casting focus-group data as ‘user reviews’	64
6.3	Backend data model	67
7	The CineFlux model	72
7.1	Theoretical grounding	74
7.1.1	Moral Foundations	74
7.1.2	Motivational Orientation	77
7.2	Model operationalization	80
7.2.1	Operationalizing moral foundations	81
7.2.2	Operationalizing motivational orientation	83
7.3	LLM prompt design for review annotation	86
7.3.1	Overview of the prompting approach	86
7.3.2	Canonical model structure	87
7.3.3	Canonical inference	89
7.3.4	Inference methodology (LLM prompting paradigms used)	93
7.4	From AI review annotation to quantified audience variables	96
7.4.1	Canonical outputs (per variable, per review)	96
7.4.2	Review x Variable scoring	97
7.4.3	Review vectors	99

7.4.4	Film- and segment-level aggregation	100
7.4.5	Activation and signed orientation at cohort level	103
7.4.6	Illustrative example	104
8	The CineFlux tool	106
8.1	Purpose and positioning	106
8.1.1	The CineFlux operational resources	107
8.1.2	A minimalistic ‘story spine’	107
8.1.3	The centrepiece: the reception map	108
8.1.4	Left panel: query and comparison controls	110
8.1.5	Right panel: the decision lens	111
8.1.6	CineFlux support for funding and policy decisions	113
8.1.7	The CineFlux innovation	114
9	Conclusions and future work	114
9.1	Limitations and risks	116
9.2	Future development and integration	117
9.3	Closing remarks	119
10	References	120

2 Document Change Log

<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Author</i>	<i>Reviewer(s)</i>	<i>Changes</i>
1.0	14.02.25	Manuel Dámasio Manuel Pita	WP7 team, tech workshop 1 (see SI WP73-A-01)	Formal definition of focus based on data-driven reception analytics measuring divergence from public to audience segmented reviews.
1.1	28.02.25	Manuel Dámasio Manuel Pita	WP7 team, tech workshop 2 (see SI WP73-A-01)	Inclusion of DK and PT as study cases. Formalization of digital focus groups as means to collect segmented audience data.
1.2	06.03.25	Manuel Pita	WP7 team tech workshop 2 (see SI WP73-A-01)	Inclusion of Letterboxd as source for public reviews.
1.3	25.03.25	Manuel Pita Mauricio Martins	WP7 team tech workshop 2 (see SI WP73-A-01)	Exploratory analysis of public reviews hinted at dimensional model based on dimensions such as morality and cultural bias. Drafted initial model
1.4	14.04.25	Manuel Pita Mauricio Martins	WP7 team tech workshop 3 (see SI WP73-A-01)	Literature review on the draft CineFlux model. Grounding computational design on theory.
1.5	12.05.25	Manuel Pita Mauricio Martins	WP7 team tech workshop 4 (see SI WP73-A-01)	Ideal model would include five dimensions. Design of focus groups for segmented demo data collection.
1.6	26.05.25	Manuel Pita Mauricio Martins Zuil Pirola	WP7 team tech workshop 5 (see SI WP73-A-01)	Initial approach to model structure and saturation with public and segmented

		Bruno Saraiva		audience data using LLM-based annotation.
1.7	09.06.25	Manuel Pita Mauricio Martins Zuil Pirola Bruno Saraiva	WP7 team tech workshop 6 (see SI WP73-A-01)	Theoretical model stable. Interaction with WP3 and WP2 for data sourcing. FG activity PT concluded and documented.
1.8	03.11.25	Manuel Pita Mauricio Martins Zuil Pirola Bruno Saraiva	WP7 team tech workshop 7 (see SI WP73-A-01)	Progress on model definition and saturation with LLMs. Update on likely features for CineFlux MVP.
2.0	17.11.25	Manuel Pita Mauricio Martins Zuil Pirola Bruno Saraiva	WP7 Lead.	LLM saturation method. Need to consider only one or two dimensions for MVP due to costs and complexity.
2.1	24.11.25	Manuel Pita	WP7 Lead.	Final annotation structure and casting annotation as interpretable quantities (activation and signed orientation)
2.2	10.12.25	Manuel Pita	WP7 Lead.	Deliverable updated with final design and scope decisions, and conclusions.
2.3	29.12.25	Manuel Pita	Maria José Brites, Manuel José Damásio	Final adjustments to deliverable document.

2.1 Statement of Originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

2.2 Disclaimer

The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

3 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents CineFlux, the minimum viable product (MVP) deliverable D7.1 for Task 7.3 in CRESCINE Work Package 7¹. CineFlux is an audience-profiling and decision-support tool designed to help funders, policymakers, and industry stakeholders reason about audiences for films from small European markets using interpretable, text-based evidence rather than opaque metrics or black-box predictions. At a high level, CineFlux does three things. First, it assembles a film corpus grounded in the small-market ecosystems studied in CRESCINE. Second, it extracts morally and motivationally relevant reception signals from audience discourse using a theory-driven large-language-model (LLM) pipeline that is explicitly auditable. Third, it presents these signals through an interactive dashboard that enables users to compare public audience baselines with segmented cohorts and to explore how different films ‘move the needle’ across moral and motivational dimensions.

The MVP was implemented on synthetic data along with a selection of films from Portugal and Denmark, with the Portuguese film further supported by segmented audience data. The design is deliberately modular and future-proof, enabling the addition of additional countries, segments, and model dimensions without redesigning the pipeline.

Corpus and data foundations. The starting point for CineFlux is the curated film list produced in WP3 for the interactive report ‘Small European Film Markets: Portraits and Comparisons’. From this, the MVP focuses on films made in Portugal and Denmark released between 2013 and 2024. For 800 titles with valid IMDb identifiers, public reviews were collected from Letterboxd using a conservative, fully documented web data collection protocol. After data

¹ The deliverable’s repository is located at <https://github.com/AISIC-Lab/crescine-cineflux>

The CineFlux MVP is located at <https://www.crescine.eu/cineflux>

cleanup and preprocessing, the final public-review corpus retained 676 films (376 PT, 301 DK, 1 co-production), with 26,529 reviews from more than 16,000 unique users.

This corpus is not a generic sample. Portugal and Denmark were selected as case studies because they offer a meaningful contrast in portfolio structure. The Portuguese film corpus contains a large proportion of documentaries and drama. In contrast, the collected Danish films have a larger share of comedy and family titles, and a broader mid-frequency spread across several additional genres. This enables the demonstration of CineFlux MVP features across distinct producer-side profiles, using the same analytical pipeline, and shows that the resulting audience indicators are not artefacts of a single genre ecology.

To demonstrate CineFlux’s capacity to connect public baselines with segmented audiences, the MVP adds a second data source: synchronous, digitally moderated focus group discussions on the Portuguese horror film *Semente do Mal* (Amelia’s Children). Ten online chat-based groups were conducted with 80 undergraduate students (18–24) from working-class Portuguese families, balanced by self-identified gender. A purpose-built platform ensured pseudonymity, controlled pacing, and a standardized moderation script that elicited participants’ own interpretive language without priming explicit moral or motivational categories.

Because CineFlux operates on review-like units, the focus-group transcripts were converted into synthetic user reviews via a conservative, multi-step process: participant turns were grouped into coherent units, then paraphrased by a multilingual LLM under a strict no-addition/no-deletion prompt contract. Each derived review is linked back to the originating turns, ensuring that all downstream annotations remain fully auditable. Public and focus-group reviews are then stored in a shared JSON backend with explicit provenance, enabling unified analysis while preserving traceability. While CineFlux was developed and validated on review samples from our entire film corpus, the MVP deliberately focuses on a small number of case-study films. This design choice reflects the computational cost of running LLM-based

annotation pipelines at scale, rather than limitations of the underlying methodology. The selected films are used to exercise the full end-to-end workflow—data ingestion, audience modelling, stance extraction, and dashboard-based interpretation—thereby validating CineFlux’s analytical logic and decision-support affordances.

Theoretical grounding and model dimensions. The audience model in CineFlux is explicitly anchored in two major dimensions of psychological and media research theory. The **Moral Foundations (MF)** dimension draws on Moral Foundations Theory, using six foundations: care-harm, equality, proportionality, loyalty-betrayal, authority-subversion, and sanctity-purity, as a structured way to capture how reviewers frame and evaluate morally salient content in the story world. In CineFlux, MF is always about what reviewers say the film and its narrative world are doing morally; it does not attempt to infer reviewers’ own stable moral identities. The dimension is motivated by empirical work showing that moral themes are visible in film narratives and that moral salience in reviews is associated with audience evaluation, preference patterns, and, in some cases, commercial performance. The **Motivational Orientation (MO)** dimension distinguishes hedonic and eudaimonic pathways in media experience. This follows entertainment research that differentiates pleasure-seeking motivations (fun, diversion, comfort, ‘a good time’) from meaning-seeking motivations (reflection, insight, grappling with moral or existential questions). CineFlux operationalizes MO through sub-variables within each pathway (e.g. humour-amusement, thrill-arousal, comfort-regulation on the hedonic side; reflection-rumination, insight-illumination, and meaning-appreciation on the eudaimonic side). The key idea is that two films can both be ‘liked’ yet for very different reasons: escapist fun versus meaningful, morally reflective engagement. Both dimensions are framed as properties of reception, not of content in isolation. What matters is how reviewers describe what the film did for them, and how they evaluate the moral and motivational aspects of that experience.

From theory to markers: model operationalization. To turn these dimensions into computable variables, CineFlux uses a canonical three-marker structure grounded in speech-

act and appraisal theory. Each variable (for example, care-harm or reflection-rumination) is inferred from review text via three sequential markers:

Trigger: whether the review invokes the construct at all under a specified scope. For MF, scope is the story world (characters, groups, institutions, events). For MO, scope is the reviewer’s own viewing experience and gratification mode.

Appraisal expression: whether the review goes beyond mere mention to offer a concrete evaluative or experiential appraisal consistent with the variable. This differentiates passing labels from genuine moral or motivational uptake.

Stance: whether the reviewer evaluates that moral element or motivational pathway positively, negatively, neutrally, or in an unclear way. This captures, for example, the distinction between ‘mindless fun’ as criticism versus ‘pure fun’ as praise, or between condemning and approving the same type of moral transgression.

Importantly, the CineFlux internal **model is based on a three-level hierarchical review abstraction**. At the top level, we have a dimension (e.g., moral foundations). Within a dimension, we have variables (e.g., care-harm), and for each variable, a three-marker structure (trigger, appraisal, and stance).

We implemented an AI engine that annotates these three markers (for every variable) in input reviews. Each annotation includes (a) an *extractive evidence span* (verbatim review quote plus character indices), and (b) a *compact justification*, ensuring that all annotations can be traced back to specific linguistic acts in the review text. This makes the model’s reasoning substrate visible and auditable for external reviewers.

Prompting architecture and LLM methodology. The CineFlux AI-based annotation engine uses an *identical* canonical prompting protocol, with parameters tuned for each variable. During annotation, the model reads an input review and answers a fixed sequence of structured

questions corresponding to the variable's trigger, appraisal, and stance. The parameters define the specific discriminant logic, appraisal cues, stance rules, and scope constraints for the variable. Outputs are returned in a strict JSON schema.

Key design choices include (a) global (review-level) interpretation rather than sentence-level tagging; (b) one variable per LLM prompt call to avoid semantic bleed; (c) conservative YES/NO decision gates for trigger and appraisal, and (d) an explicit requirement to return extractive evidence spans. The system deliberately avoids unconstrained 'chain-of-thought' explanations, favouring short, evidence-linked justifications in line with recent work on faithful rationales and interpretability. This architecture is thus reusable across dimensions. MF variables draw on the film's storyworld, whereas MO variables focus on the reviewer's self-reported experience. Additional dimensions in a broader model can be added by supplying new variable definitions under the same protocol, without altering the core pipeline.

Dashboard and decision-support functions. The CineFlux MVP exposes the model outputs through an interactive dashboard. Films from the corpus are represented in an interpretable feature space derived from MF and MO scores. Users can filter by producer country, genre, and release period; inspect film-level profiles; and compare public baselines with segmented cohorts where available. For one of the key demonstration films, *Semente do Mal* (Portugal, 2023), the dashboard shows how the segmented Portuguese student cohort re-weights the public reception baseline along specific moral and motivational dimensions, even when overall star ratings are relatively similar. This illustrates the core idea of CineFlux: 'personas' are not fixed demographic entities but dynamic evidence-based audience profiles that can be contrasted across cohorts to reveal where and how reception patterns diverge.

Note: The breadth of the corpus validates the model and pipeline; the MVP demonstrates the interface and decision logic on a limited number of films and reviews due to computational cost, not conceptual or methodological limitations.

Rationale for refinement relative to the DoA. The Description of Action (DoA) framed Task 7.3 as a ‘Personas Dashboard’ that would visualize traits of an ‘ideal’ audience for European films from small markets, drawing on earlier tasks and on dynamic inputs from WP2 and media-systemic classifications from WP3. During implementation, several factors motivated a refinement of this plan.

First, the commercial state of the art in audience-intelligence tooling advanced quickly during the early project period. Capabilities close to the originally envisaged ‘ideal audience’ functionality are now offered by commercial platforms. To preserve innovation under the CRESCINE mandate, the project focused on capabilities that such systems do not provide: a theory-linked audience model, an auditable annotation-to-score pipeline grounded in evidence spans, and a representation that enables direct comparison of public baselines with segmented cohorts. Second, upstream work packages delivered high-value inputs of a different type from what the DoA originally anticipated. WP3 provided a curated small-market film set and comparative macro-level indicators; WP2 provided rich film-characterization data. Neither, however, produced audience reception traces suitable for deriving persona traits directly. In response, CineFlux grounded persona-like profiles in the available and methodologically appropriate evidence: a large public review corpus guided by WP3, augmented through WP2’s FIDA, and segmented focus-group discussions harmonized into review-like units.

As a result, the MVP retains the DoA’s core intent: helping stakeholders reason about audiences in small European markets, but implements ‘personas’ as empirically grounded audience profiles inferred from reviews, rather than as abstract ‘ideal audience’ specifications. This reframes the ideal audience as a relational concept: stakeholders can see how a film is received and how that reception shifts for specific audience segments—a perspective that better supports evidence-based export and audience-development strategies. This refinement required additional integration work. Particularly, the collection and harmonization of segmented audience data and the stabilization of the scoring pipeline as a reproducible

process with recorded parameters and provenance. Delivery was therefore moved from Month 28 to Month 34. The extra time increased methodological robustness and auditability, strengthening the dashboard's credibility as a proof of concept.

Net contribution. CineFlux demonstrates that it is now feasible to model audience reception for small-market European films in a way that is both computationally powerful and conceptually interpretable. The MVP delivers:

1. A **curated, reproducible corpus** linking film metadata, public reviews, and segmented focus-group discourse;
2. A **theory-aligned audience model** along moral and motivational dimensions, selected because they are (i) well-established in reception and media psychology, (ii) directly observable in audience discourse, and (iii) analytically complementary—capturing value-based evaluation and experiential orientation without collapsing into generic sentiment;
3. An **evidence-constrained LLM annotation pipeline** with explicit markers and extractive rationales;
4. A **dashboard Minimum Viable Product (MVP)** that allows stakeholders to explore and compare audience profiles across films and cohorts.

While limited in scope to two producer countries and one segmented cohort, the system is designed for extension. It provides a methodological and technical foundation upon which future iterations can add more public reviews, more audience segments, additional theoretical dimensions, and deeper integration with the macro-level indicators developed elsewhere in CRESCINE, particularly in WP3.

4 Introduction

This document describes the design, implementation and demonstration of the CineFlux minimum viable product (MVP), developed under CRESCINE Work Package 7, Task 7.3. The original task in the Description of Action (DoA) envisioned a ‘Personas dashboard’ to help industry and policy stakeholders analyse audiences for films from small European markets, addressing the persistent lack of structured, evidence-based insight into how such films are received across different audience segments. CineFlux realizes this intention as a proof-of-concept decision-support tool that links film-audience discourse to an explicitly theory-grounded audience model and visualizes the resulting cohort profiles through an interactive dashboard.

At a high level, CineFlux addresses a concrete gap in current practice. Existing audience analytics solutions focus primarily on counts, ratings and black-box prediction. They rarely provide interpretable, evidence-backed explanations of *why* particular audience segments respond to a film as they do, or how those responses differ between baseline public audiences and strategically important audience segments. This lack of explanatory depth is particularly limiting for small European film markets, where public funders and producers must make high-stakes decisions under resource constraints, and where export potential depends on understanding not only how many people watch a film, but how they interpret it and what they take from it.

The CineFlux MVP tackles this problem by combining three key elements. First, it draws on two complementary sources of reception evidence: large-scale public reviews (Letterboxd) for a curated set of film reviews from small EU markets, and purpose-recruited digital focus groups for a segmented Portuguese audience discussing a selected case study. Second, it implements an audience model structured around two well-established psychological dimensions: (a) Moral Foundations and (b) Motivational Orientation (hedonic vs eudaimonic),

operationalizing them as reception variables that can be inferred from review text. Third, it uses a constrained large-language-model (LLM) annotation pipeline to extract, for each review, explicit markers indicating whether specific moral or motivational constructs are **triggered**, how they are **appraised**, and what **stance** the reviewer adopts. These markers are aggregated into film- and cohort-level profiles and surfaced in a dashboard that allows stakeholders to compare public baselines with segmented audiences in a single representational space.

CineFlux is therefore not a recommender system and not a commercial analytics product. It is a research-grade system that demonstrates how contemporary AI inference with LLMs can be embedded in a trustable, transparent and auditable workflow for audience analysis, aligned with communication and media-psychology theory and tailored to the policy and strategy questions that drive CRESCINE.

The remainder of this introduction explains how the implemented MVP refines, rather than departs from, the original DoA specification, and sets out the structure of the report.

4.1 Rationale for deviations relative to the DoA

The DoA framed Task 7.3 as a ‘Personas dashboard’ intended to visualize the traits of an ‘ideal audience’ for European films from small markets, using results from earlier tasks together with dynamic inputs from WP2 and media-systemic classifications from WP3. During implementation, two practical considerations shaped the final MVP strategy.

First, the state of the art in commercial audience-intelligence tooling advanced rapidly during the initial project period. Capabilities close to the originally envisaged ‘ideal audience’ tooling began to be offered by commercial platforms (for example, *Largo.ai*). To preserve innovation under the CRESCINE mandate, the team prioritized capabilities *not* delivered by off-the-shelf systems: (a) an explicitly theory-linked audience model; (b) an auditable annotation-to-score pipeline grounded in extractive evidence spans; and (c) a coherent comparison framework that supports public baselines alongside segmented cohorts within a single representation. For the

segmented cohorts, we introduced digitally mediated focus groups conducted at scale using an AI-supported online environment, designed explicitly for segmented audiences to discuss particular films.

Second, upstream deliverables evolved in ways that affected the type and timing of usable inputs for persona construction. WP3 delivered a curated set of films from small markets with high analytic value for reception work, and WP2 provided extensive film-characterization data. However, neither work package produced audience reception traces at the level of granularity required to specify ‘ideal audience’ traits directly. CineFlux thus grounded persona-like audience insights in the evidence that was available and methodologically appropriate for the intended use case. Guided by the WP3 film selection and augmented with WP2’s FIDA data augmentation, we collected public review corpora for the relevant titles. In parallel, and in connection with other WP7 tasks, we conducted segmented digital focus groups, the transcripts of which were converted into review-compatible units of analysis. Together, these two sources form the core data model used in the MVP.

4.2 Technology readiness level (TRL) of the CineFlux MVP

Within the Horizon Europe framework, Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) provide a standard scale for assessing the maturity of research outputs, ranging from TRL 1 (basic principles observed) to TRL 9 (actual system proven in operational environment). In that scheme, CineFlux should be understood as an upper mid-range research prototype, rather than as a production system.

First, the core methodological contribution, namely the theory-linked audience model (MF + MO), the canonical Trigger–Appraisal–Stance prompting architecture, and the JSON-based data model, has been fully specified, implemented, and partially validated on real-world data samples. The MVP runs end-to-end on films produced in two small European markets (Portugal and Denmark), using public review corpora and segmented focus-group data collected under

CresCine. This places CineFlux clearly beyond laboratory-only proof-of-concept (above TRL 4: ‘technology validated in lab’) and into the territory of validation in a relevant environment (TRL 5), where the full chain from data ingestion through annotation, scoring, and projection operates on realistic inputs.

Second, the interactive dashboard is implemented as a working MVP prototype that allows stakeholders to explore audience patterns across countries and cohorts, inspect individual reviews with evidence-linked markers, and visualize cross-cohort differences for demo case studies and synthetic data. The tool has been exercised with a limited selection of real films and real audience traces in an environment that is structurally similar to its intended use (policy and market analysis for small European film markets), but it has not yet been deployed as a maintained, production-grade system in film institutes or funding agencies. In TRL terms, this corresponds to a prototype demonstrated in a relevant environment (TRL 6), rather than a fully qualified operational system (TRL 7–9).

On this basis, we characterize the CineFlux MVP as sitting in the TRL 5–6 band: the underlying methods are implemented and validated on real data, and the dashboard functions as a coherent demonstrator for stakeholder workflows, but the system still requires further hardening, scaling, and institutional integration (e.g., deployment within film institutes’ infrastructures, routine use in funding decisions, long-term maintenance and monitoring) before it can be considered a high-TRL, operational tool.

4.3 What changed, and what remained aligned with the DoA intent

The CineFlux MVP retains the DoA’s core decision-support intent: it enables stakeholders to inspect coherence and divergence in audience traits across cohorts (public versus segmented, and domestic versus international where data are available). The refinement concerns how ‘personas’ are operationalized. Rather than attempting to define a normative ‘ideal audience’ in advance from upstream classifications, CineFlux implements personas as *evidence-based*

audience profiles inferred from observed discourse (public reviews and focus-group-derived review units). These ‘personas’ are derived through a bottom-up, data-driven analytical pipeline that uses purposefully designed AI algorithms to annotate and model audience responses across interpretive dimensions; the process is specified in §6 and §7.

Our chosen approach avoids introducing non-empirical assumptions about ideal audiences while maintaining a clear pathway for incorporating additional upstream layers as they become available. A key advantage is that ‘ideal audience’ becomes a *relational* notion: stakeholders can inspect how a film with given characteristics is received in the public review baseline, and then track how the reception ‘needle’ moves for specific segmented audiences. This relational view better supports data-driven policymaking aimed at increasing audiovisual exports in a complex, multilingual and multicultural Europe.

4.4 Prioritization, reproducibility and risk control

For the CineFlux MVP, the main technical and scientific risk lay not in the user interface but in the methodological core that establishes an auditable, reproducible mapping from language evidence to interpretable audience variables, and demonstrating that the resulting profiles are comparable across cohorts. The CineFlux MVP therefore focused on delivering a stable scoring and aggregation loop—a theory-grounded model, a constrained LLM-based annotation protocol and a reproducible backend data structure—on which user-facing dashboards can be reliably built. Workflows that approximate the originally envisaged ‘ideal audience’ specification are treated as product-stage extensions, to be activated once suitable upstream inputs and harmonized identifiers are in place.

The CineFlux architecture is future-proofed by design. It remains compatible with the later integration of WP3 outputs as contextual layers (e.g., market clusters, value-chain indicators, and policy-toolkit dimensions) and with additional WP2 descriptors, without imposing empirically ungrounded assumptions.

4.5 Schedule adjustment

The refinement of scope and method required additional work to collect and harmonize segmented audience data into a single analytical unit representation, stabilize the scoring and aggregation pipeline (including parameter logging and provenance tracking), and validate cohort comparability. Consequently, the delivery date for this task shifted from Month 28 to Month 34. The extra time was used to strengthen methodological robustness and auditability, thereby improving the credibility of the dashboard as a proof of concept suitable for scrutiny by policy and industry stakeholders.

4.6 Net effect on output value

Overall, the deviation increased the deliverable's immediate value for policy and market stakeholders. The CineFlux MVP produces transparent, reproducible cohort profiles grounded in traceable textual evidence, with extractive spans available for inspection. It supports direct comparison between public baselines and segmented audiences and offers a future-proof path for incorporating WP2/WP3 macro-context as interpretive layers. In short, the MVP delivers a more operational and auditable pathway to persona-like audience insights than initially envisaged, while remaining aligned with the DoA's overarching objective: to guide analytic reasoning about audiences in small European film markets and to support evidence-based decisions about cultural funding and audiovisual production.

4.7 Structure of the report

Following this introduction, §5 synthesizes the relevant background and state of the art in data-driven audience analytics, qualitative audience research and explainable recommender-style profiling. §6 describes the data used in the MVP, including the curated film corpus, the public-review collection pipeline, and the design and implementation of the segmented digital focus groups. §7 introduces the CineFlux audience model, detailing its theoretical grounding in Moral Foundations and Motivational Orientation, and explains how these dimensions are

operationalized as reception variables and presents the LLM-based annotation pipeline, including prompt design, saturation and scoring procedures, and the backend data model that underpins the dashboard. §8 describes the CineFlux tool interface and demonstrates how stakeholders can interrogate audience profiles, compare cohorts and explore moral and motivational patterns across films. Finally, in §9 discusses limitations, risks and avenues for future development, including potential integration with other CRESCINE work packages and with external datasets as well as our conclusions.

Together, these sections provide a comprehensive account of how CineFlux translates the DoA vision of a ‘Personas dashboard’ into a concrete, auditable MVP that advances audience intelligence practice in small European film markets. Figure 1 depicts possible ways to read this document depending on the reader’s focus and goals.

Figure 1. *Suggested reading pathways for different reader goals.*

5 Background

5.1 Data-driven audience insights in audiovisual media

5.1.1 Traditional approaches to audience research in media studies

Communication and media/reception studies have long examined how audiences engage with media content, particularly how they interpret and negotiate meaning in relation to film and television (Ang, 1985; Hall, 1980; Morley, 1980; Livingstone, 2004). Classic audience research methods have included surveys, interviews, focus groups, and ethnographic reception studies (Jensen & Rosengren, 1990; Kitzinger, 1994; Lunt & Livingstone, 1996; Krueger & Casey, 2014; Stewart & Shamdasani, 2014).

These traditional methods, while rich in qualitative insight, were limited in scale and timeliness. Audience measurement in the broadcast era relied on sampling and extrapolation (e.g., Nielsen ratings or cinema attendance counts) and often produced delayed, aggregate results. As digital media rose, conventional audience research tools like questionnaires began to show limitations in validity and timeliness. Scholars have argued that the widespread adoption of social media and other ICTs creates both challenges and opportunities, and that traditional methods risk obsolescence if they do not evolve alongside contemporary media use (Procter et al., 2015). These approaches established the conceptual basis for reception analysis, but they were poorly matched to the scale and timeliness of contemporary audience traces, motivating computational approaches that retain interpretive depth while expanding reach.

5.1.2 The datafication of audiences and rise of analytics

The media industry has undergone what observers describe as an ‘era of datafication’, in which audiences’ activities are continuously turned into data (Procter et al., 2015; Smits, 2022).

Audience analytics has emerged as a key term, referring broadly to the use of digital data to

understand how content consumption patterns and audience behaviour. One influential definition describes audience analytics as “systems and software that enable the measurement, collection, analysis, and reporting of digital data on how content is consumed and interacted with” (Zamith et al., 2020, p. 2). The outputs of such analytics are **audience metrics**—quantifiable measures such as views, clicks, shares, likes, viewing duration, and others (Zamith et al., 2020). These metrics have rapidly become ubiquitous and influential in media organizations, shaping how success is defined and how creative work is evaluated (Zamith et al., 2020).

Crucially, this datafication has elevated **audience intelligence** as a driver of strategy. In today’s media landscape, audience insights derived from online data are seen as critical to industry practices and decision-making (Mathieu & Vengerfeldt, 2020; Procter et al., 2015; Zamith et al., 2020). Major video-on-demand platforms such as Netflix and Amazon Prime Video exemplify this shift, having pioneered big-data strategies that build knowledge systems around large-scale viewer data, algorithmic analytics, and individual consumer preference tracking (Alva, 2025). These companies leverage detailed viewing histories and behavioural patterns to inform content development and recommendations, illustrating how consumer data now directly shapes creative and business choices.

Beyond the tech giants, the broader film and exhibition sector has begun to engage with data. Film festivals and cinema exhibitors, traditionally not data-driven, are experimenting with online platforms that automatically collect audience data—for example, streaming analytics for hybrid festivals (Smits, 2022). Industry analysis notes that since the mid-2000s, annual audience reports and data insights have grown in importance for cultural events, partly due to stakeholder demands and the availability of digital analytics. In essence, audience research has been reinvigorated by digital data, moving from small-sample surveys to the continuous monitoring of audience behaviour across platforms.

This shift also means harvesting new types of audience behaviour data. Online video platforms can pinpoint precisely when viewers start or stop watching a film, and which parts they ‘binge on’ or abandon—information that was largely inaccessible to traditional methods (Smits, 2022). Social media platforms add another dimension: they serve “not simply as a new source of data about audiences but as a new forum for unprecedented interaction and collaboration with the audience” (Procter et al., 2015, p. 470). Audiences now actively produce content (comments, shares, likes) that becomes valuable feedback data.

Datafication therefore expands the evidence base for reception analysis, but it also pushes organizations towards metrics that are easy to count and hard to interpret, creating a need for models that can translate audience traces into inspectable claims about meaning, values, and disagreement.

5.1.3 AI-powered tools to obtain audience insights

With the explosion of big audience data, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning techniques have become central to extracting meaningful insights. Modern audience analytics goes beyond counting metrics; it uses AI to detect patterns, predict trends, and personalize content delivery. Key AI-driven methods in the current state of the art include:

AI now underpins most large-scale audience analytics, from recommender systems and segmentation to performance prediction, sentiment analysis, and cross-platform integration (Alva, 2025; Katsaounidou et al., 2025). These systems improve operational decision-making, but they typically optimize for prediction and engagement while obscuring how audiences interpret content and why groups disagree (Procter et al., 2015; Zamith et al., 2020).

Indeed, incorporating AI in this context is not without challenges. In news media, for instance, there is an ongoing debate about the role of analytics and metrics in editorial decision-making and the risk of metric-driven pressures on journalistic values (Procter et al., 2015; Zamith et

al., 2020). Creative industries similarly worry that data could override human creativity or introduce bias. Emerging perspectives, therefore, emphasize AI as a support for, rather than a replacement of, human insight. Furthermore, as we discuss later, these state-of-the-art frameworks lack the means to explain what they have learnt about audiences.

Søltoft and Munk (2025) propose the concept of **'recalcitrant audiencing'** to describe a mode of audience analytics in film production that challenges filmmakers' assumptions instead of offering definitive, fixed representations of 'the audience'. In the case study of a Danish data consultancy working with film projects, the authors used the output of algorithmic analyses to spark discussion, explore multiple potential audiences, and open narrative space for renegotiation, rather than to dictate creative choices (Søltoft & Munk, 2025).

Existing AI audience analytics optimize for expected audience behaviour but obscure interpretation. CineFlux uses AI to make audience meaning, values, and disagreement legible for cultural and policy decisions at scale.

5.1.4 Dashboards and decision support for audience analytics

Data-driven audience insights are most valuable when presented in intuitive and actionable formats. Dashboard interfaces and analytics platforms have therefore become a crucial part of the ecosystem. Dashboards serve as centralized, interactive tools where domain experts—whether media executives, marketing teams, or policy analysts—can monitor key audience indicators and drill down into specifics. A typical audience analytics dashboard might display real-time viewership trends, demographic breakdowns, engagement funnels (e.g., how users progress from a trailer to a full watch), and content performance comparisons, all updated in real time.

Conventional dashboards optimize visibility of metrics. CineFlux redefines the dashboard as an interpretive workspace, enabling stakeholders to interrogate audience meaning, value conflicts, and cohort-specific responses rather than consume decontextualized indicators.

Media organizations have widely adopted such tools. In journalism, for instance, newsrooms use real-time analytics dashboards to see which articles are trending, how long readers stay, and where they come from, embedding audience metrics into everyday editorial workflows (Zamith et al., 2020). This is another example of the trend as mentioned earlier: editors, producers, and even film festival organizers increasingly rely on data displays to guide their actions--for instance, to promote a popular story, adjust a marketing campaign, or program an encore screening for a highly streamed festival film (Smits, 2022).

Contemporary dashboards are also growing more sophisticated by incorporating AI-driven features. Some systems highlight anomalies or spikes in audience activity (using anomaly-detection algorithms) to alert teams to unexpected behaviour. Others include predictive widgets--such as forecasting tomorrow's audience size based on current trends--or embedding recommendation engines that suggest content or campaigns to prioritize (Alva, 2025). User interface design focuses on clarity and interactivity: users can filter data by audience segments, time ranges, or content types and obtain visualizations (graphs, heatmaps, geographic maps) that make patterns evident at a glance. Katsaounidou *et al.* (2025), for example, present a dashboard for news impact analysis that combines survey results with attention-tracking data in an interactive visualization, illustrating how multimodal data can be delivered to researchers and practitioners in a single tool.

5.1.5 *Data-driven audience insights*

Beyond commercial optimization, data-driven audience insight techniques are increasingly applied across the cultural sector and public policy. **Audience development** is a key concept in arts and cultural policy, encompassing strategies that aim to widen, diversify, and deepen cultural participation. Traditionally, cultural institutions (museums, theatres, public service broadcasters, film festivals) relied on ticket sales, basic demographic data, and periodic surveys to gauge their audiences. There is now a clear shift toward more **evidence-based, data-driven policy support** for cultivating audiences and justifying public investment in culture.

Recent research in Europe exemplifies this trend. Visanich *et al.* (2025), for example, demonstrate how AI can enhance audience development for a national arts centre. In their study of Malta's national centre for creativity, the authors deployed computer vision sensors to count foot traffic (people passing by and entering the venue) and used machine learning to forecast attendance patterns. The authors then mapped movement data and combined it with survey feedback to identify not only who visits the cultural site and when, but also who does not visit and why (Visanich et al., 2025).

These insights informed targeted outreach strategies. For instance, if data indicated that certain times or demographic groups showed low engagement, the institution could adjust programming or communication to convert 'non-visitors' into visitors (Visanich et al., 2025). This case illustrates how big data on audience behaviour, including outside the digital realm, can guide decision-making to improve cultural access and resource allocation. The authors report that integrating AI-driven insights with traditional audience research (such as on-site surveys) yielded concrete recommendations for audience growth and ultimately contributed to increased visits and participation. Such evidence-based work aligns directly with EU cultural policy goals on inclusion, participation, and accountability.

Film festivals offer another pertinent example. Smits (2022) shows that festivals have entered the data age by leveraging online and hybrid formats that automatically generate analytics on viewers. Organizers can now gather data on how audiences interact with online screenings—for example, how many people watched a film, from which locations, and for how long (Smits, 2022). These data complement classic post-festival surveys and help festivals provide stakeholders (including public funders and sponsors) with a more quantitative picture of their audience reach and engagement.

Film and audiovisual decisions are not made solely within platforms; they are also shaped in professional meeting points where projects, partners, and expectations are negotiated. Research on co-production platforms associated with festivals shows that these spaces function as strategic sites of mediation at the intersection of industrial and creative logics, where professionals exchange information, calibrate standards, and orient attention in contexts of abundant supply and dispersed demand (Euvrard et al., 2018).

CineFlux is designed for intermediary cultural decision settings—including festivals, co-production platforms, and funding contexts—where intelligence must be interpretable, comparable across audiences, and grounded in traceable evidence that supports discussion rather than automation (Euvrard et al., 2018; Smits, 2022).

One festival director interviewed by Smits (2022) notes that “you can get so much data now: for example, when people started the film, when they got tired, and what they liked”, underlining how streaming data can reveal detailed viewing habits. Yet, data at scale does not automatically translate into actionable explanations. Festivals still value surveys for qualitative insight, but automated analytics offer scale and immediacy. Smits (2022) highlights the case of Göteborg Film Festival, which used both system-generated data and an extensive survey to evaluate its online edition, recognizing that new data opportunities can **complement rather than replace**

traditional audience research. This synergy is emblematic of the current state of audience studies in culture: data analytics provide breadth, while reception studies complement it with depth.

From a policy perspective, such practices support more agile and informed cultural management. Governments and cultural agencies increasingly seek data-driven insights to justify and refine policies—for example, by analysing attendance patterns to guide funding allocations or by monitoring audience demographics to ensure diversity and inclusion goals are met. For instance, AI-driven audience development work in Malta explicitly argues that data-rich, AI-enabled audience analysis can help cultural institutions pursue more inclusive and evidence-based strategies (Visanich et al., 2025).

It should also be acknowledged that not all cultural organizations have the resources or capacity for advanced analytics, and concerns about privacy and ‘techno-driven’ approaches are legitimate. Smits (2022) notes that some festival professionals are ambivalent about the extent to which they wish to rely on online audience data, especially given wider controversies around datafication and algorithmic governance. There is an ongoing discussion about maintaining a balance between quantitative data and the qualitative values of culture, and about ensuring that data use is GDPR-compliant, ethically robust, and transparent. Nonetheless, the overall trajectory is clear: data-driven audience insight is becoming a cornerstone of modern cultural management, offering tools to engage audiences more effectively while providing accountability for cultural investment.

5.1.6 Implications of the state of the art for CineFlux’s design

The literature on data-driven audience insight has converged on a practical baseline: contemporary systems combine multiple data sources, automate analysis at scale, and deliver results through interactive dashboards that support near-real-time monitoring and comparison (Procter et al., 2015; Zamith et al., 2020; Smits, 2022; Alva, 2025). This evolution matters here

less as a catalogue of techniques than as a set of design requirements that any credible audience-insight tool must satisfy. First, **multi-source integration is no longer optional**. Audience behaviour is distributed across platforms and settings, and the most informative analyses combine heterogeneous evidence rather than privileging a single stream. This directly motivates a workflow that can compare public, large-scale traces with carefully characterized qualitative audiences, while preserving a common representational unit so that comparisons remain meaningful (Smits, 2022; Søtoft & Munk, 2025).

CineFlux implements cross-source integration by mapping reviews and ratings from any source onto a standard audience model, and by treating structured, moderated discussion outputs as focus-group-like reception units that can be analysed with the same variables (as we unpack in §5.2 and §6.2.2). This supports direct comparisons between public traces and segmented audiences.

Second, the state of the art has created an accountability gap. Many widely deployed approaches generate strong predictive performance but provide limited explanatory clarity about what has been learnt regarding audience motivations, values, and reception patterns. This matters in cultural and policy contexts, where decision-makers need reasons that can be inspected and debated, not only forecasts or aggregate engagement metrics (Zamith et al., 2020; Søtoft & Munk, 2025).

Audience insight systems should favour representations that remain legible to domain experts and traceable to evidence, even when the underlying computations rely on machine learning. CineFlux prioritizes this transparency by design as we show in subsequent sections.

Third, ‘no net effect’ is often does not mean ‘no reception’. Aggregate metrics can collapse distinct audience dynamics into superficially similar summaries. For instance, an average sentiment near zero may reflect indifference, but it may also reflect polarization. This is a general limitation of mean-based reporting, and it motivates reporting schemes that separate prevalence of discussion from direction of evaluation, and that preserve the option to inspect the underlying evidence when ambiguity remains (Procter et al., 2015).

CineFlux analytics avoid collapsing indicators as averages if they do not capture true audience features or obscure underlying knowledge hidden in the source data.

Finally, dashboard delivery changes what counts as a useful output. In practice, audience insights must be presented in forms that support filtering, comparison, and narrative interrogation by non-technical stakeholders. This shifts emphasis away from single headline scores and towards structured, inspectable summaries that can be broken down by film, cohort, or segment, and then traced back to the underlying textual evidence when required (Zamith et al., 2020; Katsaounidou et al., 2025).

Taken together, these strands imply a concrete target for CineFlux. The tool must support cross-source comparability, produce interpretable constructs aligned with audience theory, and retain a clear audit trail from quantitative summaries back to the original audience language. The remainder of this deliverable specifies how these requirements were operationalized through the data design (§6), the audience model (§7), and the dashboard workflow (§8).

5.2 Focus groups

In the context of CineFlux, focus groups play a specific and strategic role. Unlike large-scale digital trace data, focus groups allow researchers to work with *explicitly defined, demographically and culturally characterized audiences*, producing reception data whose

social context is known rather than inferred. This makes focus groups uniquely valuable for studying how particular audience segments interpret, evaluate, and negotiate meaning around audiovisual works. In other words, they provide high-resolution, segment-specific evidence of audience reception that cannot be recovered from anonymous online reviews alone.

At the same time, the very properties that make focus groups analytically powerful—contextual depth, controlled recruitment, and rich interaction—also constrain their scalability. It is this tension, between interpretive precision and analytical reach, that motivates CineFlux’s methodological design.

Indeed, media producers, funders, distributors, and critics, both in the film industry and academia, have long sought to understand segmented audience behaviours through qualitative research, yielding deep insights into audience reception, particularly regarding emotional responses, behavioural change, and cultural interpretation.

In industry, qualitative methods have guided marketing decisions since the 1920s. Finola Kerrigan (2017), in *Film Marketing*, noted the longstanding use of focus groups to gather audience feedback and inform promotional strategies and film edits. More recently, Wyatt (2024), in *Creating the Viewer: Market Research and the Evolving Media Ecosystem*, has shown that various qualitative methods, including focus groups, still prevail in industry to understand audience demands and tastes better. However, a key issue addressed by CineFlux is that many of these methods lack the rigour, structure, and scale needed to gain the complete trust of decision-makers.

5.2.1 Focus groups and reception studies

Academic research started using focus groups in the 1940s, when Merton and Lazarsfeld used group discussions to explore audience responses to media content (Lunt & Livingstone, 1996; Merton, 1987). After a period dominated by quantitative surveys, qualitative methods,

particularly focus groups, regained prominence in the 1970s and 1980s, driven by theories that focused on the audience's active role in interpreting media. Stuart Hall's influential encoding/decoding model explains how audiences actively construct meanings rather than passively consume media (Hall, 1980). Studies by Morley (1980) and Liebes and Katz (1990) further demonstrated how focus group discussions reveal collective interpretations influenced by social and cultural contexts, providing crucial insights complementary to quantitative data such as audience ratings.

Throughout the 1990s and early twenty-first century, qualitative audience research expanded significantly, integrating methods such as ethnography, interviews, and particularly focus groups. Henry Jenkins' influential fan studies showed how communal interactions shape audience experiences (Jenkins, 1992). Researchers became more attentive to group composition and moderator influence: groups of friends or family typically produced more natural discussions, while groups of strangers provided diverse perspectives (Kitzinger, 1994; Lunt & Livingstone, 1996). The ideal level of moderator involvement was also debated; less structured approaches allowed for genuine participant-driven interactions, whereas more structured methods improved comparability (Cyr, 2016; Krueger & Casey, 2014b; Stewart & Shamdasani, 2014). Remote moderation emerged as another option to enhance authenticity (Prosser et al., 2024)

Researchers selected methods based on their objectives, favouring open-ended conversations for exploratory studies and structured moderation for evaluative research. Analytical strategies advanced from simply coding individual statements to examining interactions themselves, influenced by conversation analysis and dialogism, recognizing that group discussions yield collective interpretations not evident from isolated individual responses (Markova et al., 2010).

It is worth noting that as audience studies expanded globally, researchers applied focus group methods in diverse contexts, sometimes comparing audiences across nations (Cuenca-Amigo & Makua, 2017; Moretti et al., 2011). Transnational reception studies have examined how audiences in different countries respond to the same Hollywood blockbuster or global TV format. For example, Martin Barker coordinated large-scale qualitative audience projects (blending surveys with open-ended responses and group components) for films like *The Lord of the Rings*, revealing variations in emotional and moral reactions across national cultures (M. J. Barker, 2005; M. Barker & Mathijs, 2008). While such projects often involve hundreds of participants, they preserve a qualitative spirit by asking viewers to write or talk in their own words about their interpretations and feelings. The cumulative lesson from comparative qualitative studies is that audience activity—liking, interpreting, critiquing, feeling—is deeply inflected by social location.

In sum, for more than a century, in both industry and academic settings, qualitative research methods have played a crucial role in understanding how audiences engage with film, television, and other audiovisual media. Among these methods, the focus group has been especially prominent as a tool for exploring audience tastes, interpretations, experiences, social dynamics, and emotional responses. Unlike digital trace data, focus groups uniquely allow researchers to pinpoint and analyse carefully selected, specific audiences. Note that digital reviews and social media comments rarely provide demographic context about who is writing. In contrast, focus groups explicitly bring together known participants, ensuring a detailed understanding of audience identity and social dynamics. Placing a purposefully recruited group of participants in a moderated setting allows researchers to observe not only individual reactions but also the complex negotiation of meanings and interpretations within a social context.

5.2.2 Focus groups at scale

The standard focus-group method faces significant limitations when researchers attempt to scale and generalize findings beyond small, context-specific groups. Let us consider three relevant limitations.

1. Focus groups (as well as interviews and ethnography) have traditionally been *time-, cost-, and labour-intensive to implement*. These methods require securing an appropriate space, recruiting and compensating participants, securing a convenient time, paying a human moderator for their labour, transcribing the recordings, and analysing and writing up the findings.
2. Precisely because of these time and labour costs, *small sample sizes* have been used, restricting generalization to larger populations, a critical concern in media research (Anis & Olisa, 2024; Pilcher & Cortazzi, 2024). Thus, qualitative methods typically lack the statistical rigour needed to establish causal relationships between media exposure and behavioural outcomes clearly, especially in large, comparative studies (Pilcher & Cortazzi, 2024; Sainy, 2024).
3. Because of the small sample sizes (and the traditional need to conduct in physical spaces), qualitative audience research frequently focuses on *culturally homogeneous groups*, limiting its applicability across diverse cultural settings (Merrington et al., 2019). Overcoming this limitation often requires methodological triangulation, combining qualitative approaches with other analytical frameworks (Schrock et al., 2022). Conducting qualitative research across linguistic and cultural boundaries introduces substantial translation and interpretation challenges, further complicating cross-cultural analysis (Pilcher & Cortazzi, 2024).

This methodological gap—between the depth offered by small, context-rich qualitative data and the breadth of large-scale digital trace data—remains largely unresolved. Sociologists and

communication scholars have long argued that meaningful audience analysis requires contextual depth and careful demographic characterization; yet they increasingly recognize the limitations of small-scale, labour-intensive methods in addressing broader, network-scale audience dynamics in a timely manner (Kümpel & Anter, 2024; Lareau, 2011; Small, 2010).

5.3 From black-box profiles to nuanced AI insights

In the audiovisual domain, audience profiling traditionally relies on data-driven recommender system techniques applied to user ratings. Collaborative filtering and other latent-factor models use patterns in ratings to model user preferences, often yielding abstract, dense vector (embedding) representations or latent features for users and items (Pan et al., 2020). While effective for prediction, these models operate as black boxes; their learned representations are not readily interpretable. For example, a matrix factorization or neural recommender might cluster users with similar viewing histories, but it cannot explicitly explain what unites those users beyond the math. Most latent factor approaches often lack interpretability, making it difficult to understand the contribution of specific features to a recommendation (Fusco et al., 2019; Pan et al., 2020). Likewise, complex deep learning recommenders can achieve high accuracy but provide little to no insight into *why* a user would like an item, highlighting an accuracy–interpretability trade-off in recommender design (Fusco et al., 2019; Pan et al., 2020).

In practice, this over-quantification reduces rich audience tastes to opaque numbers, making it difficult to glean a nuanced understanding of audience motivations. Current systems may excel at answering *‘who likes what?’* but struggle with *‘why?’* because they lack an explicit explanatory framework of audience psychology.

The heavy focus on numeric metrics (ratings, clicks, views) in today’s models often comes at the expense of qualitative nuance. Aggregated scores and broad segments paint an incomplete picture of the audience. For instance, a recommender might identify a large cohort

that gave high ratings to action films. Still, this quantitative grouping obscures why those films appeal, whether the attraction lies in fun escapism, suspense, moral heroism, or meaningful social commentary. Moreover, as streaming platforms have learned, optimizing content purely to chase broad, measurable appeal can lead to shallow outcomes. Netflix’s data-driven foray into content production, for example, has been criticized for producing the so-called ‘algorithm movie’: formulaic films engineered to hit the *widest* audience metrics yet lacking distinctive substance (Hoad, 2025). Indeed, when the platform began making films *guided by data aimed to please a vast audience*, the results were often generic and forgettable, illustrating the danger of an over-quantified approach that prioritizes scale over depth.

Such models offer little in the way of a human-understandable rationale that creative executives or funders can use. In strategic decisions—such as green-lighting a film or allocating a marketing budget—stakeholders need more than *‘the algorithm predicts success’*; they need a nuanced explanation of *why* a target audience would engage. Industry-facing guidance on audience research similarly stresses that effective audience analysis must *move beyond surface-level demographics* to uncover underlying motivations, behaviours, and needs. Indeed, there is growing recognition that purely quantitative profiles are insufficient. We require interpretable insight into audience psychology to complement the numbers.

What is missing from these approaches is not more data, but a way to explain audience reception in terms of interpretable motivations, values, and evaluative orientations.

This limitation is central to CineFlux’s design: the system does not aim to outperform recommender engines, but to recover the explanatory dimensions that conventional audience profiling obscures. The first step in explaining the ‘why’ questions related to audience reception is to situate them within relevant dimensions. We review two such dimensions below. These will be the pillars on which the rest of the deliverable is built.

5.3.1 Explanatory dimensions for audience reception

Motivational orientation. One critical dimension of audience psychology that current systems often ignore is the motivational orientation behind content choices—particularly whether audiences seek hedonic or eudaimonic experiences. *Hedonic* motivations involve seeking pleasure, fun, and excitement from media (e.g., light-hearted entertainment or adrenaline-fueled thrills). *Eudaimonic* motivations involve seeking meaning, insight, or emotional depth (e.g., thought-provoking narratives or emotionally complex storytelling).

Media psychologists Oliver and Raney (2011) demonstrated that audiences have distinct hedonic and eudaimonic motivations for consuming entertainment. They developed scales that show people do not watch movies only for ‘fun and pleasure’; many also turn to entertainment for purposes of ‘truth-seeking’, grappling with life’s purpose and human meaningfulness (Oliver & Raney, 2011). In other words, a comedy and a tragic drama might both earn 5-star reviews, but likely for very different reasons: one delivered laughs (hedonic gratification), the other a profound reflection (eudaimonic appreciation). Standard recommender models treat those two 5-star ratings as equivalent signals of “liking”, thereby missing crucial nuance.

In response, some researchers have proposed incorporating hedonic/eudaimonic dimensions directly into recommender models. Tkalčič & Ferwerda (2018) introduce theory-driven recommendations that explicitly model hedonic and eudaimonic movie preferences, inferring a user’s orientation and labelling movies accordingly. Their work illustrates how **motivational orientation** can enrich audience profiles beyond genre or rating alone. An audience member’s balance of hedonic vs. eudaimonic preferences can, for example, explain why they favour slow, reflective dramas over fast-paced blockbusters (or vice versa), offering a more **causally informative profile** than traditional behavioural signals (Tkalčič & Ferwerda, 2018).

Moral orientation. Beyond motivational goals, moral and value orientation is another factor influencing audience reception. Viewers bring personal values and moral frameworks (e.g.,

attitudes about fairness, care, authority, purity) that shape how they respond to narratives and characters. Traditional recommenders generally do not account for this dimension, but emerging studies show it is significant.

A recent computational analysis of approximately 1.6 million film reviews found that the **moral salience** of audience reviews correlated strongly with a film's success (Huang et al., 2024). Using the Moral Foundations Dictionary, the authors examined references to moral domains—such as care, fairness, loyalty, and authority. They found that films with higher moral salience in reviews tended to have higher audience ratings, greater popularity, and higher revenue. Movies that prompted moral reflection in audiences thus enjoyed a measurable boost in engagement and appraisal, suggesting that *moral resonance* is a key component of audience appreciation.

On the individual level, moral inclinations clearly impact user behaviour. Nokhiz and Li (2017) analysed Yelp reviews. They showed that moral language in user-generated content helps explain rating behaviour: reviewers who expressed moral concerns systematically rated differently, often giving lower ratings when a moral foundation was perceived to be violated. This work demonstrates that a person's moral orientation—what values they prioritize and what offends them—affects how they evaluate and endorse experiences (Nokhiz & Li, 2017).

Ignoring this nuance, a recommender might erroneously group users who rate a film low for very different reasons—one due to pacing or technical quality, another due to moral disagreement. Explicitly profiling moral orientations would enable more sensitive recommendations (e.g., avoiding content that clashes with a user's core values), and even more importantly in the context of this deliverable, yield richer explanations: *“This segment of the audience cherishes themes of justice and reacts poorly to perceived injustices in a storyline”*. It moves us toward understanding audiences as *humans with values*, not just data points.

Apart from having identified the dimensions on which we can situate our audience reception questions, it is also necessary to contextualize and chart the means to answer them at scale, with large volumes of data.

5.3.2 Toward explainable, nuanced profiles with language models

To address the limitations mentioned above, researchers are turning to **large language models (LLMs)** and advanced NLP as tools for audience profiling. The same textual data that recommender systems historically compress into single sentiment scores—reviews, comments, social posts—contains fine-grained signals about motivations, values, and interpretations. Language models can *read* and interpret this content with a degree of nuance that approximates human analysis but at a much larger scale. Several methodological avenues become possible:

Inferring hedonic/eudaimonic signals from text. LLMs can be prompted to detect whether a review reflects hedonic enjoyment or eudaimonic appreciation. For example, an LLM analysing a user’s movie reviews might identify words and phrases indicating fun, e.g., ‘hilarious’, ‘thrilling’, ‘a wild ride’, versus those indicating meaningful impact: ‘thought-provoking’, ‘inspiring’, ‘left me reflecting’. The ability to aggregate extracted features across user reviews enables the model to infer, for instance, that *User A* consistently emphasizes learning and self-insight (an eudaimonic orientation). In contrast, *User B* foregrounds excitement and humour (hedonic orientation). These **implicit signals become explicit variables** in the audience profile.

Extracting moral stances from reviews and comments. Building on infrastructures like Moral Foundations Theory, fine-tuned language models (e.g., BERT variants or GPT-like models) can identify value-laden language in reviews more flexibly than simple keyword matching. Drawing on the logic of Nokhiz and Li’s (2017) study, an LLM could score user texts along care, fairness, loyalty, authority, and sanctity dimensions, or generate qualitative summaries such as: *“This audience segment often praises acts of loyalty and is disturbed by violations of purity norms*

in stories”. In this way, **moral orientation** becomes an interpretable component of the audience profile, derived directly from user discourse.

Generating human-readable explanations for recommendations. Unlike latent factors, language model outputs are inherently textual and interpretable. This property is directly leveraged in recent work on explainable recommendations. Ma *et al.* (2024) propose *XRec*, a model-agnostic framework that integrates collaborative signals with LLMs to generate explanations for recommendations. Their framework aligns graph-based collaborative filtering with an LLM via a lightweight adapter, *XRec* produces *‘comprehensive explanations’* of user-item interactions that are grounded in user behaviour but expressed in natural language (Ma et al., 2024). In an audiovisual context, a language model-enhanced system might not only predict that *User X* will enjoy *Movie Y* but also explain: *‘You are likely to enjoy this film because it aligns with your preference for morally complex, meaningful narratives (eudaimonic appeal) and strong themes of fairness’*. This goes beyond generic templates like *‘Users similar to you liked this’*; and provides reasons rooted in the user’s expressed values and motivations.

Enhancing decision support for cultural and funding decisions. Making audience traits explicit enables language-model-based profiling to improve decision-making for content creators, marketers, and policy-makers. Rather than depending on simple metrics, decision-makers gain a more detailed explanation of why a project may resonate with its target audience. For example, a funding committee evaluating a socially engaged film might be informed that *“the targeted audience segment exhibits high eudaimonic motivation and frequently reflects on moral growth in their reviews; this project’s narrative strongly aligns with those orientations.”* Such an explanation, grounded in large-scale textual evidence, has nuance and persuasive power that pure statistics lack.

More broadly, explainable AI research emphasizes that systems must provide both accurate predictions and transparent rationales, especially when their outputs inform consequential

decisions (Fusco et al., 2019; Ma et al., 2024; Pan et al., 2020). In cultural policy and funding contexts, this requirement is particularly salient: stakeholders need to understand *how* and *why* AI-driven insights connect a piece of content to specific audience groups.

In summary, current audience-profiling methodologies in recommender systems remain heavily centred on opaque representations and overly quantified views of users. They often miss the *why* behind audience preferences—the moral values, emotional goals, and motivational orientations that drive engagement. The resulting audience profiles are optimized for behavioural prediction but offer limited explanatory value, making them ill-suited as stand-alone evidence for cultural strategy or funding decisions.

Language model-based approaches represent a promising innovation that directly addresses these state-of-the-art limitations. Using advanced natural language processing, LLMs can analyse reviews and ratings to infer explicit audience characteristics like hedonic versus eudaimonic motivation and moral stance. These dimensions, long discussed in communication and media psychology, are rarely put into practice on a large scale (Huang et al., 2025; Oliver & Raney, 2011; Tkalčič & Ferwerda, 2018). The quantified variables mapping nuanced moral and motivational dimensions can then be integrated into dashboards and decision-support tools as human-readable descriptors, enabling explanations like: *“This film resonates with audiences who seek meaningful, morally reflective experiences,”* rather than simply *“This film scores 4.3/5 with 18–34-year-olds.”*

Such an approach does not replace existing recommender methods; instead, it adds an interpretable and, importantly, explanatory layer on top of them, reconnecting large-scale data analysis with the conceptual richness of audience and reception studies. For cultural institutions and policymakers, the goal is to provide a path toward evidence that is both computationally powerful and theoretically informed: audience analytics that can speak to values, meanings, and motivations rather than only numbers.

Through this deliverable, we position language-model-based, explicitly interpretable audience profiling as a key methodological innovation: one that transforms audience data into an explanatory framework robust enough to support not just optimization, but also **transparent, justifiable decisions about cultural funding and audiovisual production.**

5.4 Interpretive value of reviewer stance

In audience reception studies, **reviewer stance** refers to the explicit evaluative position a reviewer takes on specific dimensions of a film (e.g. moral appraisal, aesthetic quality, narrative credibility). Far from being a trivial personal opinion, a reviewer's explicit stance carries significant interpretive and analytical value for understanding how audiences make meaning from media. This section explains why identifying—and situating—stance signals in film reviews is crucial for analysing audience reception in CineFlux. Drawing on reception theory, media psychology, and computational audience modelling, we show how stance reveals audiences' meaning-making processes, illuminates audience segmentation by values, and provides an actionable abstraction for large-scale analysis of collective reception patterns.

5.4.1 *Stance as evidence of meaning-making processes*

Audience reception theory has long held that meaning is actively constructed by viewers, not passively absorbed (Hall, 1980). Stuart Hall's encoding/decoding model famously demonstrated that audiences may accept, negotiate, or oppose a film's preferred meaning depending on their social position and values. In this context, a reviewer's stance on a film's moral or thematic elements is a direct window into their interpretive process. For example, a reviewer who explicitly condemns a protagonist's unethical actions or praises the film's virtuous message reveals how they decoded the film's moral meaning. Such stance-taking is an essential aspect of the reviewer's *reading* of the film—a concise statement of the meaning or value they derived from it. Identifying stance signals is therefore invaluable for reception analysis because they externalize the normally internal process of meaning-making. As Janet

Staiger notes, audience responses (including critical stances) are textual evidence of interpretation, showing how people connect media content to cultural frameworks and personal experiences (Staiger, 2005). When a reviewer makes an evaluative statement—for instance, about a film’s moral stance—they are actively negotiating the film’s meaning within their own moral framework, illustrating the broader process by which audiences make sense of media.

Crucially, stance provides insight into *why* an audience member responds as they do. Media psychology theories indicate that viewers’ moral and emotional appraisals of characters significantly shape their enjoyment and appreciation of a story. According to affective disposition theory, audiences continuously judge the morality of characters’ actions, rooting for those they deem ‘good’ and reviling those they consider ‘bad’, which in turn affects their emotional engagement and satisfaction with the narrative (Raney, 2006; Zillmann, 1988). In other words, audience members form moral evaluations that guide their reactions. A reviewer’s explicit moral appraisal of a film (e.g. finding a character’s behaviour reprehensible or laudable) thus highlights the moral judgments that underlie their response.

These judgments are key to understanding the meaning the reviewer made of the film: whether they saw it as upholding justice or glamorizing wrongdoing, aligning with their personal ethics or challenging them. As Oliver and Bartsch (2011) observe, audiences often experience a deeper form of appreciation—distinct from simple enjoyment—when entertainment prompts them to reflect on human virtues and moral truths. For instance, a reviewer who praises a film for ‘inspiring contemplation about right and wrong’ is signalling that the film elicited this meaningful, virtue-based mode of engagement. Stance statements of this kind indicate that the viewer derived eudaimonic gratification (insight, moral reflection) rather than or in addition to hedonic pleasure (Oliver & Bartsch, 2011). In sum, when articulating how a film aligns or conflicts with certain moral or thematic expectations, the reviewer’s stance provides a concrete trace of the interpretive and affective processes—moral evaluation, identification, emotional payoff—through which audiences derive meaning from media content.

5.4.2 Stance: audience segmentation, and value alignment

Beyond individual meaning-making, reviewer stance signals are analytically powerful for revealing **audience segmentation** and **value alignment** within the broader audience. Audiences are not monolithic; different groups of viewers may interpret the same film in divergent ways depending on their values, ideologies, and cultural backgrounds (Hall, 1980; Staiger, 2005). A reviewer's stance often implicitly identifies the value position from which they approached the film, and comparing stances across reviews can thus highlight distinct interpretive communities. For example, if some reviewers laud a film's portrayal of vigilante justice as morally justified while others condemn it as glorification of violence, we can infer the presence of (at least) two audience segments aligned with different moral frameworks. These segments correspond to what Zillmann (2000) termed 'morality subcultures' (or taste cultures) defined by shared moral intuitions. Each sub-audience brings its own assumptive world to the act of viewing, resulting in systematically different readings of the same cultural object. Identifying a reviewer's stance on key issues (such as whether a film's ending is morally uplifting or troubling) allows researchers to classify which audience sub-group that reviewer may represent or speak to. In effect, stance markers serve as signals of audience identity since they let us segment responses by ideology, moral outlook, or other value-laden perspectives.

Moreover, stance analysis sheds light on **value alignment** between media content and its audiences. Audiences tend to respond more favourably to content that resonates with their own values and beliefs (Haidt, 2012). When a reviewer's stance enthusiastically endorses a film's moral viewpoint or thematic message, it often indicates that the film's underlying values align with that reviewer's value system—and likely with that of a broader like-minded segment of the audience. Conversely, a negative stance (e.g. a reviewer taking offense at the film's politics or ethics) signals a misalignment between the film's implied values and those of certain viewers. This is essentially an instance of what (Hall, 1980) described as an oppositional reading—the audience member understands the text's preferred meaning but rejects it from

their own value position. From an analytical perspective, mapping these alignments and misalignments is crucial for understanding a film's reception. A film that polarizes reviewers on moral grounds, for instance, is likely provoking contested meanings among the audience, whereas a film that garners uniformly positive moral appraisals is probably aligning with widely shared values or hegemonic norms (Hall, 1980; Staiger, 2005).

Representing reviewer's stance explicitly as data (e.g. 'Reviewer A approves of the film's feminist stance' vs. 'Reviewer B finds the film's feminist stance off-putting'), allows researchers to investigate how audience values influence reception. This approach resonates with findings in moral psychology that different people prioritize different core values (e.g. care, fairness, loyalty, authority), leading to divergent reactions to the same content (Haidt, 2012). Indeed, recent studies demonstrate that audience responses can be clustered by the moral foundations they invoke: for example, a film might appeal strongly to viewers high in moral valuing of care and fairness, while alienating those who prioritize loyalty or authority, or vice versa (Huang et al., 2024). In practical terms, analysing stance allows scholars to segment the audience by worldview and examine how value alignment with a film's themes correlates with reception outcomes like satisfaction, debate, or controversy.

5.4.3 Stance markers in computational audience modelling

Perhaps most importantly for contemporary research, a reviewer's explicit stance on defined variables (such as moral appraisal) provides a **computationally tractable abstraction** for modelling audience reception at scale. In the past, reception studies relied on qualitative analyses of small samples (interviews, focus groups, see §5.2.1) to infer audience interpretations. Today, however, the availability of large datasets of online reviews and comments has enabled computational approaches that treat stance markers as data points. Thus, with an automatic and trustworthy stance annotation in thousands of reviews, researchers can quantify patterns in how audiences respond to media content. This abstraction—representing each review in terms of *situated* and *nuanced* stance signals on key

dimensions—enables rigorous analysis of collective reception trends that would be impossible to discern anecdotally.

For instance, as noted previously, Huang et al. (2024) employed computational content analysis of 1.6 million film reviews to examine moral stance at scale. They used a lexicon-based approach grounded in Moral Foundations Theory to measure moral sentiment in each review and found that the salience of moral evaluations in reviews was strongly associated with positive audience reception and even commercial success. In particular, films that elicited frequent moral commentary (e.g. invoking issues of care, fairness, loyalty, authority) tended to have higher audience ratings and box-office revenues (Huang et al., 2024). This suggests that when audiences engage with a film on a moral or ethical level, it can indicate deeper involvement and broader resonance. Such findings validate the idea that **stance markers are not only interpretively meaningful but also predictively useful** for understanding reception. Through casting reviews into a structured set of stance indicators (e.g., whether the reviewer approves or disapproves of the film’s morality, politics, or realism), one can apply data-driven techniques to map audience reactions. Clusters of reviews with similar stance profiles may represent distinct audience segments, as discussed above, and these can be correlated with external factors like demographics or viewing platforms (Evans & Aceves, 2016). Furthermore, tracking stance frequencies over time or across a film corpus can reveal macro-level trends in audience sensibilities, such as increasing moral sensitivity in reviews of specific genres (Huang et al., 2024). In short, an explicit stance signal can **bridge qualitative insight and quantitative analysis**: it translates rich, subjective commentary into signals that can be analysed without losing the connection to meaning and values.

Another advantage of using stance as an analytical construct is that it facilitates **value-alignment analyses in identifying ideal target markets**. Computational models can be designed to detect when a piece of content—e.g., a film—is likely to cause a value clash in certain audience segments by examining stance-laden feedback. For example, natural

language processing models can perform stance detection to automatically classify whether a review is for or against a film’s moral messaging. This has been used in social media analytics to gauge public opinion on controversial issues (Küçük & Can, 2020; Mohammad et al., 2016), and similar techniques are easily applied to media reception. The combination of stance detection with audience modelling enables researchers and industry analysts to identify how different subgroups respond to the same film. **This is a fundamental aspect of the CineFlux system described in this deliverable.** This approach aligns with broader trends in computational social science of using textual data to model cultural reception (Evans & Aceves, 2016). It treats each stance-laden review as a data point in a high-dimensional ‘response space’ where dimensions correspond to interpretive variables like moral approval, emotional intensity, ideological agreement, and so on. Analysing patterns in this space can uncover latent structures in audience reception—such as polarization on certain values or convergence in interpretations among certain communities.

In summary, a reviewer’s explicit stance on specific model variables provides a vital analytical handle for audience reception research. **Stance encapsulates the outcome of complex interpretive processes in a form that is communicable and measurable,** linking individual meaning-making to collective audience trends. It offers insight into how and why audiences derive particular meanings (through moral and evaluative framing), how those meanings vary across groups (reflecting value-based audience segmentation and alignment), and how we can systematically analyse these phenomena at scale (through computational modelling of stance markers). CineFlux thus recognizes stance as a succinct yet profound abstraction, one that condenses the richness of audience response into a form amenable to analysis without stripping away the human values and judgments that drive reception.

6 The data

We mentioned in §5 that CineFlux leverages two different data sources to support this deliverable, namely,

1. **Public** (unsegmented audience) film reviews from Letterboxd, and second,
2. User ‘reviews’ extracted from focus-group activities for which we recruited participants in specific **audience segments**.

The goal of this section is to characterize these data sources formally.

6.1 The films sample

A key output from Work Package 3 (WP3) is a curated film dataset purposefully assembled to analyse distribution, export markets, and international circulation within the CresCine ecosystems. It was developed under WP3, *Small Film Markets: Comparative and Cross-sectional Perspectives*, in close coordination with WP2’s work on data infrastructure and with the State of European Film platform.

WP3’s primary objective was to establish a robust conceptual and empirical framework for understanding small European film markets through a comparative, cross-sectional analysis of key industry indicators. The main output is the interactive report *Small European Film Markets: Portraits and Comparisons*, which brings together more than 30 quantitative indicators on production, distribution, exhibition, and reception across seven small European ecosystems—Denmark, Estonia, Croatia, Ireland, Lithuania, Portugal, and Flanders/Belgium—covering the period 2014–2022.

Within that report, the section ‘Export markets and international distribution’ (Cathrin Bengesser and Marius Øfsti) draws on a harmonized, film-level corpus derived from the LUMIERE Pro database of the European Audiovisual Observatory (EAO). This corpus is the

WP3 dataset used here: a cleaned and enriched subset of LUMIERE Pro data, structured to address CresCine’s research questions on how small European film markets perform—within and beyond their domestic territories—in terms of export, circulation, and admissions. Because the dataset is grounded in EAO data, it is anchored in official, widely used European industry statistics. This improves the credibility of the resulting analyses, supports comparability with established policy and industry work, and still leaves room for tailoring to the specific needs of small-market research.

For the CineFlux MVP, we used a subset of the WP3 dataset comprising **films produced in Portugal or Denmark released between 2013 and 2024**, containing **954 titles in total**. We completed the collection of public Letterboxd reviews for the **800 films** in the subset that had valid IMDb identifiers. This sample was augmented through FIDA to obtain extended film characterization data. We henceforth refer to this augmented dataset as the **film corpus**.

Denmark and Portugal were selected for the CineFlux MVP as two small European producing contexts that provide a useful contrast in the composition of the available film corpus. As shown in Figure 2 , the Portuguese set is strongly concentrated in documentary and drama. In contrast, the Danish set contains a comparatively larger share of comedy and family titles and a broader spread across several mid-frequency genres. This contrast strengthened the MVP demonstration: it allowed CineFlux to be exercised on films emerging from two distinct producer-market profiles, using the same review-based evidence pipeline, and to show that the resulting audience-profile indicators are not artefacts of a single genre ecology. This evidence supports a **producer-context** rationale (content mix and portfolio structure); it does not, on its own, establish cross-national audience differences, which require matched segmented-audience data.

Figure 2. Film genre distribution for the two producer contexts used in the CineFlux MVP (Portugal vs Denmark). Counts show how the available film corpus is distributed by genre in each country. Portugal's set is concentrated in documentary and drama, while Denmark has a relatively larger share of comedy and family titles and a broader mid-frequency spread across additional genres. This contrast motivated the use of DK and PT as a producer-side demonstration pair, ensuring that the CineFlux MVP is exercised across distinct portfolio profiles rather than within a single genre ecology.

6.1.1 Data characterization and preprocessing

This report summarizes the exploratory data analysis (EDA) the film corpus. We retained the following film attributes:

- `imdb_id` – unique identifier for each film.
- `title` – film title.
- `year` – release year (later coerced to numeric).
- `production-country` – (list of country codes, e.g., PT, DK).
- `genres` – list of genre labels (strings).

The film corpus contained 800 films initially. The production-country split (as recorded in the production-country field) is nearly even: 413 titles are classified as Portugal (PT) and 388 as Denmark (DK). No additional production countries were present in the provided data; the residual set of films not labelled PT or DK is empty. The sum of PT and DK is 801 because one of the films is a co-production between PT and DK.

6.1.2 Collection of public-review data

We collected 156,121 public reviews from the Letterboxd platform for films in the film corpus. The collection of Letterboxd reviews followed a transparent, reproducible pipeline designed to balance empirical coverage with compliance and methodological rigour. With the target film sample in hand, we established source access. Letterboxd remains the preferred venue for audience reviews given its volume and interaction features, but access conditions are non-trivial. The official API is in private beta and currently not granted for data-analysis or LLM-related projects; as such, we treated API access as unavailable and followed a cautious web data collection approach restricted to publicly accessible pages, with request pacing,

caching, and explicit adherence to the platform's terms of use. Each run recorded the collection window, user agent and throttle parameters so that subsequent updates are comparable and auditable.

The harvesting routine, per film, resolved the canonical Letterboxd URL and paginated deterministically across review index pages up to the site's practical ceiling, which, in our prior runs, captured up to 3,072 reviews per film given the typical 256-page cap with 12 items per page. For each review we extracted stable attributes that are directly observable without client-side execution: the reviewer handle and profile link, the star rating represented as Unicode including half-stars, the review date as displayed on the page, the full review text when present, the like count at time of capture, and the permalink to the comment thread when the review has replies. When available, associated comment threads were traversed and normalized into a list of atomic messages with author, timestamp and text. All fields were stored as plain text at capture time and only transformed in analysis layers, avoiding irreversible normalization within the raw store.

Quality control operated at two levels. At capture stage, the collector validates page structure, retries idempotently on transient failures, and records HTTP status, response hashes and timing metadata. At consolidation stage, the dataset is de-duplicated on the tuple of film-id, reviewer-id and review-date, while soft conflicts, such as edits to review text between passes, were retained as latest-wins but flagged to preserve provenance. Where site pagination or visibility constraints limit total recall, we documented those ceilings per film and carried them forward into any comparative analysis to avoid overstating representativeness.

Ethical and legal considerations are addressed explicitly. Only public content was collected, no attempt is made to access private endpoints, and request pacing is tuned to be conservative relative to site responsiveness. We stored profile links but did not retained sensitive user attributes beyond those already publicly displayed on the review page. All

analyses derived from this public-review corpus are reported with the relevant caveats about sampling frames, pagination limits and possible survivorship or platform biases. Furthermore, we applied pseudo-anonymization to all reviewer handles, and indeed only used review text for downstream tasks. The Cineflux MVP neither reproduces any Letterboxd data points nor allows access to them in our backend data server. We do not even reproduce harvested reviews—used as input for LLM-based annotation and for downstream aggregation (see §7).

Finally, the pipeline is designed to be rerunnable. Each execution is tied to a manifest specifying film inputs, time bounds and tool versions, enabling like-for-like refreshes as new reviews accrue or as the film set evolves. Outputs were written in a schema compatible with the shared ‘Letterboxd data model’ so that different projects—EDA over WP3 films, moral foundation annotations, or audience-profile prototypes—can interoperate without per-project forks of the ingestion layer.

We found that 49 films had no reviews, so we excluded them. Additionally, to recover a comparable film sample within the ‘typical’ regime in terms of the number of reviews, and to control costs associated with downstream LLM-based model saturation from data (see §7), we applied the standard interquartile range (IQR) method to eliminate outliers. Thus, films with public review counts below or above $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ were excluded from the film corpus. **This reduced the sample from 800 to 676 films**, retaining the substantial majority of titles while excluding the most extreme cases. The resulting boxplot in Figure 3 makes the underlying structure visible: the median and quartiles can be compared directly, and the overall variability of review counts can be assessed without distortion from a few very high-volume films.

6.1.3 The final public-review corpus

After removing outliers using the Interquartile Range (IQR) method, we retained a subset of 676 films, comprising 376 from Portugal (PT) and 301 from Denmark (DK); one film is co-produced by PT and DK, which explains the overlap in country totals. This filtered, **public**

review corpus contains 26,529 reviews in total, of which 12,159 are for Portuguese films, and 14,543 for Danish films. As shown in Figure 3, DK films have slightly more reviews on average (median 25) than in Portugal (median 15). Review text remained predominantly short-form: the distribution of review lengths (in words) was Q1 = 7 words, a median of 19 words, and Q3 = 54 words (see Figure 4). Participation also remained broad after outlier removal. In this subset, Portuguese films were reviewed by 7,072 unique users, whereas 9,376 unique users reviewed Danish films (see Table 1).

Descriptive feature	PT	DK
Number of films	376	301
Number of reviews (total)	12K	14K
Number of reviews per film (central tendency)	15	25
Review length (central tendency, number of words)	19	20
Number of unique reviewers	7K	9K

Table 1. *Descriptive overview of the public review corpus (Portugal vs Denmark). Summary statistics for the two country subsets used in the MVP, reporting corpus size (films, reviews, unique reviewers) and typical review density and verbosity (median reviews per film; median review length in words).*

Figure 3. Review-volume distribution per film in the public review corpus (Portugal vs Denmark). Boxplots summarize the number of public reviews per film, showing a strongly right-skewed distribution in both countries with a long tail of highly reviewed titles. Denmark exhibits a higher typical review volume than Portugal (whereas both corpora include a small number of extreme outliers with more than 200 reviews).

Figure 4. Review length distribution in the public review corpus (Portugal vs Denmark). Boxplots compare review length (word count) across countries. The two corpora show very similar typical review length, with Denmark marginally higher at the median (20 vs 19 words), and comparable dispersion (PT IQR 7–56; DK IQR 8–53). Total reviews analysed are shown below each box (PT: 12,159; DK: 14,543).

We found similar annual film-release rates for DK and PT in the period for which data were collected, with an expected dip in 2020 and 2021 due to the COVID-19 pandemic (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. *Film coverage over time in the public review corpus (Portugal vs Denmark). Year-by-year counts of films represented in each country subset, with smoothed trend lines indicating how the corpus coverage varies across release years (2013–2024).*

6.2 Focus-group data

To demonstrate one of the key contributions of the CineFlux approach to data-driven audience analytics, we conducted digital focus groups (FGs) centred on a Portuguese film for a specific Portuguese audience segment. This allows CineFlux to materialize the quantification and explanation of **how a known audience segment re-weights the generic audience portrait derived from public reviews.**

The film *Amelia's Children*. (Semente do Mal, original title), released in 2023, and directed by Gabriel Abrantes. This is a horror film, notable for its unconventional and provocative thematic elements. The narrative revolves around Edward, who, upon discovering his biological family

through a DNA ancestry service, travels to rural Portugal with his girlfriend, Riley. Their reunion with Edward's estranged mother, Amelia, and twin brother, Manuel, quickly evolves into a disturbing exploration of familial bonds, obsession with eternal youth, and dark, occult practices deeply rooted in local folklore. The film is characterized by a deliberate blend of psychological horror, grotesque imagery, and dark comedy. It navigates unsettling themes such as incest, extreme plastic surgery, and occultism, presented within a uniquely Portuguese cultural context.

The film has generated polarized reactions among audiences, ranging from fascination and appreciation for its bold thematic choices and visual style to outright discomfort and moral aversion due to its explicit content and poor narrative development. This divisive reception reflects the film's provocative engagement with themes of identity, morality, and cultural specificity, making a compelling case study for audience reception analysis.

This focus-group corpus has already been used in prior work to demonstrate the 'moving needle' concept that underpins CineFlux (Pita et al., Forthcoming). In that study, we combined traditional focus-group methods with Natural Language Processing to place public online reviews and focus-group discussions for *Amelia's Children* in a shared semantic space. Public reviews provided a large, organically generated baseline, while carefully recruited focus-group participants supplied a demographically defined, context-rich comparison segment. Mapping both sources into the same representational frame made it possible to show how specific audiences re-weight interpretive dimensions such as cultural identity, humour, moral values, and emotional responses when they discuss a film collectively rather than individually.

The present deliverable generalises and systematises that approach. CineFlux extends the earlier 'moving needle' demonstration from a semantic-space comparison to an explicit audience model grounded in Moral Foundations and Motivational Orientation, with every shift between public and segmented cohorts expressed as movements in a common, interpretable

variable space. The focus-group corpus for *Amelia's Children* thus serves both as a substantive case and as a testbed for validating the pipeline that links qualitative depth to scalable, data-driven analysis.

The primary motivation for selecting this film as a case study is its distinctive blending of traditional Portuguese rural settings, cultural motifs, and nuanced social dynamics, all conveyed through a predominantly Portuguese cast. Intriguingly, despite its rich local authenticity, the film is delivered in English. This linguistic choice strategically enhances its accessibility and exportability to international audiences, thereby enabling researchers to examine how national cultural elements are received, interpreted, and negotiated within broader global markets.

The target segment: undergraduate students (18–24 years) enrolled in the same university; evenly balanced by self-identified gender. **Recruitment** was by invitation via contact with lecturers; first-come, first-served until ten seats per group were filled, following (Morgan, 1997), ten participants maximize turn-taking richness while avoiding conversational overload in written chat.

The total number of unique participants across all sessions was 80 students. Of these, 36 self-identified as male, 35 as female, and nine either preferred not to disclose their gender or identified as 'other gender'.

Viewing condition. All confirmed participants watched the film together, either in an on-campus auditorium or via online streaming. Viewings (on campus and streaming) took place between 30 and 90 minutes before the chat session.

Digital setup. We created a purpose-designed platform for synchronous WhatsApp/Discord-style group chats, with a bot serving as the moderator—**CineFlux FG**. The platform ensures that (a) all users have a random username generated by the system, (b) can prompt the user to answer a range of pre- and post-debate questions, (c) allows the implementation of a

remotely controlled, semi-autonomous moderator bot that deploys the moderation script (see details below), (d) automatically controls the speed at which messages appear in the chat interface to ensure readability and maximize interactions, and (e) contains an explicit reply affordance to ensure people can target their interaction, which is an important interpersonal coordination mechanism in multiparty mediated chats.

Moderator script. The automated moderator delivered eleven prompts (Q1–Q11). The scripted questions were adapted from standard film-audience questionnaires (Prosser et al., 2024):

1. Does the film match your views on the producer country’s culture?
2. What is the most suitable genre classification?
3. Who is the most surprising character?
4. What are the most outstanding scenes or memorable lines?
5. What would be your two-sentence pitch for a friend?
6. Can you agree on a synopsis?
7. What would you change?
8. Would you recommend it?
9. Cinema or streaming?
10. Did the film change your views on the producer’s country cinema?
11. Are there other opinions you consider important?

Script rationale. Questions deliberately avoid sentiment-laden vocabulary such as ‘good’, ‘bad’, ‘best’, or ‘worst’, preventing lexical priming that could artificially influence overlap with identified review clusters. The moderator bot refrains from paraphrasing or expanding upon user responses, thus ensuring that lexical content remains authentically participant-generated.

We did not include questions that explicitly named or directly operationalized the moral and motivational dimensions (elaborated below in §7.1) of our audience model in the focus-group moderation script. This decision aligns with the purpose of the groups, which was to surface

participants' own interpretive frames—how they talk, justify, and disagree—without first teaching them the analyst's vocabulary. Focus group methodologists consistently caution against 'theory-labelled' or leading questions that steer participants towards the researcher's categories rather than their own; question routes are typically designed to invite concrete accounts, followed by gentle probing that remains anchored in participants' language and examples (Kitzinger, 1994; Krueger & Casey, 2014a; Morgan, 1997).

This is particularly salient for constructs with normative charge. Questions that foreground 'morality' can trigger demand characteristics—participants infer what the study is 'about' and adjust their contributions accordingly—while also amplifying social desirability pressures that are already heightened in a public, group setting (Orne, 1962; Tourangeau & Yan, 2007, 2007). Rather than invite performative alignment with an abstract dimension, we treated the dimensions as analytic lenses applied after collection: moral and motivational signals are recoverable from naturally occurring evaluative language, accounts of intention, attribution of responsibility, and justificatory narratives, without naming the dimensions in the elicitation itself (Barbour, 2007).

Moderator dynamics. The moderator bot was configured to (a) wait 80 seconds after the last human turn before posting a reminder of the currently active prompt, and (b) wait another 40 seconds before posting the next prompt in the script. This design choice seeks to avoid premature cut-offs in the conversation.

6.2.1 Structure of the collected data

For the CineFlux MVP the only **pre-debate CineFlux FG asked every user was** 'How do you rate the film you'll be discussing about today on a 1-5 scale?' the answer of which was stored along with basic sociodemographic data for the user. The main unit of data was participants' conversational turns. Hence, the data was structured and collected in the following manner: (a) `timestamp`, (b) `user_name`, (c) `turn_text` (captured verbatim). Usernames were

generated by the system (auto-pseudonymization), whereby only a separate consent ledger links codes to identities, thereby ensuring participants' anonymity and safety.

We collected 1530 turns over ten FG sessions. The median number of conversational turns per session is 148 (interquartile range, IQR = 22). The proportion of turns classified as phrasal (containing at least one complete sentence) is 70.98% (1086 turns). The median number of turns per user was 14 (IQR=7).

6.2.2 Casting focus-group data as 'user reviews'

CineFlux integrated two complementary sources of audience reception data: (i) public reviews (e.g., Letterboxd) and (ii) audience segmented focus-group discussions. These sources differ in form—public reviews are already written as compact standalone texts, whereas focus-group data is conversational and turn-based. To enable unified downstream processing, CineFlux converts focus group transcripts into *review-compatible* texts that preserve participants' original meanings while aligning with the review unit of analysis.

Rationale and design constraints. The purpose of the conversion is representational compatibility, not interpretation. CineFlux must preserve the informational content of the discussion while producing a stable text unit that can be handled by the same annotation and scoring pipeline used for public reviews. Two constraints follow. First, the conversion must be **loss-minimizing** with respect to semantic content: it should not drop evaluative statements, justifications, or meaning-making reflections that participants express. Second, it must be **non-creative**: the conversion must not introduce new claims, new interpretations, or new causal links beyond what is supported in the transcript.

All segmented discussions in the dataset are **single-film sessions**: each focus group is conducted about one target film only. This design avoids cross-film ambiguity and allows the

conversion process to treat all references within the transcript as belonging to the same film context.

Step 1. Turn extraction by participant and film. For each focus-group session, CineFlux identifies the set of participants and extracts the ordered sequence of turns for each participant within the target-film discussion. The extraction preserves the original order and associates each turn with identifiers required for auditability (e.g., participant ID, session ID, turn index, and—where available—timestamps).

The output of this step is a participant-specific turn stream:

- one stream per participant,
- scoped to a single film,
- represented as an ordered list of turns with provenance identifiers.

Step 2. Folding turns into coherent review units (without inference). Text-mediated group chat is naturally fragmented. Participants often express a single point across multiple short turns, self-correct, or complete an idea after brief interruptions. If CineFlux paraphrases raw turns directly, the resulting text becomes either incoherent (too fragmentary) or encourages the model to ‘fill in’ missing connective data. CineFlux therefore applied a conservative pre-processing step termed **folding** to recover semantic units.

Folding merges turns into sentences (review units) **only when this improves coherence without changing meaning**. The rule is merge for coherence, never merge to infer. Operationally:

- CineFlux folds **only within-speaker** contributions; content is never merged across different participants.

- CineFlux folds turns that jointly realize **one semantic act** (one claim, evaluation, justification, or reflection) that is merely split across boundaries.
- CineFlux does **not** fold across genuine topic shifts, even for the same speaker; these become separate semantic acts (review units).
- Non-semantic utterances (backchannels, fillers, purely logistical remarks) are excluded unless they add meaning (e.g., suggesting empathy).

Each folded unit retains a provenance list of the source turn IDs, ensuring that any extracted review can be traced back to the exact transcript spans that generated it.

Step 3. Paraphrase into review format using a multilingual LLM (GPT-4.0). The set of folded participant review units was converted into a review-style text using a multilingual large language model (GPT-4.0). The model is used strictly as a *paraphraser*, not as an interpreter. The instruction regime enforces two constraints:

- **No content addition:** do not introduce new facts, motives, or explanations not present in the source unit.
- **No content deletion:** do not remove evaluative language, commitments, or meaning-relevant detail; compress only redundancies created by conversational repetition.

The paraphrase output is a compact text that resembles a public review in form: a standalone reception statement, expressed in natural language, that preserves the participant’s original claims and evaluative stance as expressed in the FG transcript.

Where discussion occurs in languages other than English, the multilingual capacity of GPT-4.0 supports paraphrase without requiring an intermediate translation step. If a unified language is required for a specific analysis view, translation can be applied as a separate, explicitly logged pipeline operation, distinct from paraphrase.

Step 4. Representation compatibility and auditability. After paraphrasing, each extracted review was stored using the same top-level review structure as public reviews, including review text, language metadata, and a provenance field linking back to the originating focus-group session and turn identifiers. This ensures that:

- The same canonical annotation prompts work on both public and segmented texts.
- Downstream scoring and projection treat both sources identically.
- Every annotation remains auditable, because both the paraphrased review and its underlying transcript spans are available for inspection.

Further relevant methodological information on the focus-group-to-review conversion—covering (i) the folding heuristic used to define review units, (ii) the paraphrase prompt contract (template plus prohibitions), and (iii) the minimal provenance schema for traceability—is provided in Supplementary Information² (SI) WP73-B-01.

6.3 Backend data model

Figure 6 and Figure 7 describe the CineFlux data model. The design serves three deliverable-grade requirements: **auditability** (every inference can be checked against the source data), **reproducibility** (the same pipeline configuration yields the same outputs), and **comparability** (stable outputs across films, countries, languages, and data sources).

The structure separates film-level containers from review-level analysis units. Film-level objects organize metadata, aggregated scores², and review collections by provenance. Review-level objects preserve the canonical AI (LLM) annotations and the derived numeric vectors used by the MVP for scoring, modelling, and dashboards. This separation avoids duplication,

² All Supplementary Information documents are available at <https://github.com/AISIC-Lab/crescine-cineflux>

prevents ambiguity about the source of a score, and guarantees that any aggregate can be traced back to the precise evidence span that triggered it.

More concretely, at the root of the data model (see Figure 6), three fields exist for governance and traceability. `schema_version` fixes the data contract version, `generated_at_utc` fixes when the dataset was produced, which matters for reconciliation across runs. `pipeline` captures the effective processing configuration (model versions, scoring weights, filtering decisions, and any other parameters that materially affect the outputs). Together, these fields provide the minimum information needed to reproduce results and defend them during review.

Under films, each entry is keyed by `{imdb_id}` as a stable identifier for integration with external sources. Each film contains:

1. `metadata`, holding descriptive attributes (English title, release year, Letterboxd URL and score, genres, production countries, languages, and related fields). This block exists to support filtering and segmentation in the tool.
2. `scores`, holding film-level aggregated metrics. CineFlux keeps a dedicated score for MF (mf, moral foundations, see §7.1), and splits Motivational Orientation into `mo_hedonic` and `mo_eudaimonic`. This allows CineFlux show whether a film's reception is driven by pleasure-oriented or meaning-oriented uptake—or by both—and whether these patterns differ between public baseline and profiled segments.
3. `reviews`, explicitly grouped by provenance: public for platform data (e.g. Letterboxd) and segmented for focus-group-derived material. Within segmented, each segment `{S1, S2, S3, ..., SN}` includes `segment_name`, `segment_description`, and `collection_protocol`, alongside the review items. This is the point where methodological context is stored with the data, so that later interpretive claims remain

defensible and do not conflate organic platform behaviour with structured, moderated collection settings.

Each review (see Figure 7) is the central analysis unit in CineFlux. For that reason, every element in items (whether public or segmented) is organized into three blocks with distinct roles. The first block carries the raw material: `review_id`, `review_text`, `embeddings`, `user_rating`, `lang`, and any other review-level fields. This preserves the original text and the minimum context needed for downstream analysis (for example, language filtering and rating-conditioned comparisons).

The second block, **annotations**, stores the model's canonical inference output, variable by variable. For Moral Foundations, this is `mf`: `{Y: CANONICAL_ANNOTATION_OBJECT}`. For Motivational Orientation, this is `mo`: `{pathway_Y: CANONICAL_ANNOTATION_OBJECT}`, implemented through pathway-prefixed variable names, e.g. `hedonic_*`, `eudaimonic_*`. See §7.1 for details. This keeps MO flat for computation while still making pathway membership explicit and machine-readable. Each `CANONICAL_ANNOTATION_OBJECT` contains three LLM annotations for a review + variable pair: (i) `trigger_identified`, (ii) `appraisal_expressed`, and (iii) `reviewer_stance`. Every annotation is accompanied by an extractive evidence span with character offsets. This is the core audit mechanism: any user can inspect exactly what fired, and why, without relying on opaque model internals or narrative 'explanations' that cannot be verified.

The third block, **derived**, contains the numeric representations CineFlux uses operationally. These include `mf`, `mo_hedonic`, `mo_eudaimonic`, and `combined`, where `combined` is the concatenation in the defined order (`MF + MO hedonic + MO eudaimonic`). These vectors do not replace the canonical annotations. They provide a stable, compact representation for scoring, clustering, visualization and dashboards, while the canonical objects retain the evidence and the decision logic needed for scrutiny.

This data model **externalizes the reasoning substrate** of the system. Film-level scores can be defended with traceable intermediate decisions; review-level decisions can be defended with direct evidence; and provenance is preserved so that comparisons between public baseline and profiled segments remain methodologically sound. The result is a backend that supports a stakeholder-facing tool without sacrificing accountability: every headline metric on the dashboard can be traced back to the exact quote span that triggered it, under a known pipeline configuration and a published schema version.

Figure 6. Film-level CineFlux MVP JSON structure: each film record bundles metadata, aggregated MF and split MO (hedonic/eudaimonic) scores, and review collections separated into public sources and segmented focus-group corpora (S1, S2, ...) with segment descriptors and protocols.

Figure 7. Review-level CineFlux MVP JSON structure: each review stores raw fields (text, rating, embeddings, language), canonical per-variable annotations (trigger, appraisal expression, stance) for MF and MO variables, and derived numeric vectors for MF, MO-hedonic, and MO-eudaimonic, plus their concatenated combined vector used as the analysis unit for scoring and visualization.

7 The CineFlux model

We discussed (§5) how state-of-the-art ‘audience analytics’ in the audiovisual sector remain **behavioural and metric-first**: engagement traces (views, completion rates, likes/shares), segmentation, prediction, and optimization loops. This can be operationally powerful, but it tends to **quantify attention rather than uncovering the likely drivers of that attention**, and it often stabilizes norms around ‘what performs’ instead of helping decision-makers understand *why* a work resonates (or fails) across different publics (Procter et al., 2015; Zamith et al., 2020). CineFlux was designed address this gap by targeting a different object: **audience reception as expressed cultural explanation**, extracted from natural language at scale with explicit evidence and auditable reasoning.

CineFlux is innovative in *how* it creates audience insight: it operationalizes reception via **theory-defined dimensions** (Moral Foundations and Motivational Orientation, see §5.3.1) and a robust **canonical AI LLM prompting** approach that forces each inference to be externally grounded, thus transparent, auditable and explainable. Concretely, each dimension is defined with an explicit **scope** (story-world vs reviewer-experience), and a hierarchy of variables that saturated (with data) through,

- a. Evidence for the variable’s presence in an input review
- b. Lexical/pragmatic cues signalling reviewer appraisal and
- c. The reviewer’s appraisal stance ‘positive/negative/neutral/unclear’

This approach moves beyond the current focus on attention (and often sentiment): it produces **dimension-specific, interpretable reception markers** with quote spans and indices, enabling transparent aggregation into variable and dimension-level scores without losing audibility. Our approach is consistent with emerging arguments that posit analytics should *challenge* creative and policy assumptions rather than dictate them, i.e., ‘recalcitrant audiencing’ (Søltoft & Munk, 2025).

Crucially, we will show in subsequent sections how this design matches European priorities because it is oriented to **public value and cross-border circulation**, not only market prediction. The Creative Europe programme explicitly frames its goals around safeguarding and promoting **European cultural and linguistic diversity**, strengthening the sector, and supporting cross-border reach and audiences (European Commission, 2023; Regulation (EU) 2021/818). In addition, EU-level policy has recently emphasized (i) improving the **cross-border circulation of European audiovisual works**, (ii) leveraging digital transformation and audience data to build meaningful relationships with **diverse audiences** and support evidence-informed policymaking. CineFlux directly operationalizes these aims by making **cultural meaning legible at scale**: it helps identify *which* audiences in *which* contexts

align with a film’s moral and motivational ‘pathways’, where misalignment occurs, and what kinds of framing/support may improve circulation and reception across national and subcultural publics.

In practical terms, CineFlux supports decision needs aligned with core European values that conventional dashboards do not address well: funders and policy stakeholders often need to justify choices in terms of **cultural diversity, inclusion, and intercultural exchange**, not just predicted demand³. Grounding audience insight in explicit theoretical constructs, and tying outputs to traceable evidence, strengthens three important variables at once: **accountability** (why a conclusion was drawn), **comparability** (consistent markers across countries and corpora), and **actionability** (which audience-development interventions are realistically plausible, contextualization, framing, targeting, or mediation). This is aligned with current EU policy emphasis on audience development, discoverability of diverse content in digital environments, and evidence-informed cultural strategy.

7.1 Theoretical grounding

7.1.1 Moral Foundations

The Moral Foundations (MF) dimension in CineFlux considers six variables: *care-Harm*, *equality*, *proportionality*, *loyalty-betrayal*, *authority-subversion*, and *sanctity-purity*. The MF dimension is grounded in a central line of cognitive-psychological work on moral judgement that explains how people detect morally relevant cues, appraise them, and form evaluative reactions. Moral Foundations Theory (MFT) argues that moral reasoning and moralized perception are structured around a small set of foundational concerns, with systematic variation across individuals and groups in which concerns are most salient (Graham et al., 2009, 2013). This is directly relevant to film reception because reviews often disagree not only on aesthetics but

³ Council of the European Union 2021, 2024 (see [EUR-Lex+3culture.ec.europa.eu+3stradalex.eu+3](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/3stradalex.eu+3))

on what the narrative is ‘doing morally’: what counts as harm, betrayal, illegitimate authority, unfairness, or sanctity violation in the story world, and whether the film is perceived to condemn, excuse, or value those elements.

In CineFlux, **moral foundations are always applied only to the film’s story world as audiences describe it**: reviewers moralize events, characters, and norms within the film’s narrative. We therefore treat MF as a reception dimension over story content, rather than as a direct measure of reviewers’ stable moral traits.

Empirical work supports the idea that moral content is visible in both film narratives and reception. In film, moral themes have been linked to audience evaluations and performance outcomes (Huang et al., 2024). Separately, an emphasis on moral values is associated with broader ideological patterns that can plausibly manifest in review language and reception dynamics (Federico & Malka, 2021; Graham et al., 2009; Weber & Federico, 2013). Recent research also indicates that moral and ideological orientations can contribute to polarization in review ecosystems, including coordinated negative reviewing around controversial titles and widening gaps between critic and audience scores (Amendola et al., 2015; Cantone et al., 2025; Day & Kim, 2023). Previous work by our team on Rotten Tomatoes is consistent with this framing: we observed systematic critic–audience differences in moral-ideological language and corresponding differences in contexts in which critic and audience ratings diverge (Günes et al., 2024).

Classical MFT proposed a single ‘fairness–cheating’ foundation. Recent large-scale psychometric work has revised this into two distinct but related foundations—equality and proportionality—while retaining care, loyalty, authority, and purity (Atari et al., 2023). CineFlux adopts this six-foundation scheme because it maps cleanly onto reception of contemporary films: equality tracks concerns about equal treatment of social groups and social justice

themes, while proportionality captures merit- and deservingness-based fairness (e.g., whether characters ‘get what they deserve’).

Finally, recent work has connected these psychological variables to reception. Individualizing and binding foundations predict movie preferences (Gehman et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2024). In CineFlux, these foundations therefore function as a compact vocabulary for how audiences morally frame what happens in films—what they recognize as care, injustice, betrayal, legitimate authority, or violation of sanctity—and thus as one of the core axes along which reception can systematically diverge across cohorts. Table 2 presents details of the variables that constitute the MF dimension.

Variable	Definition (psychology)	In film reviews
Care-harm	Care-harm refers to sensitivity to others’ suffering, compassion, and the motivation to protect or help the vulnerable or those in distress.	Care-harm emerges in stories or evaluations that highlight empathy, kindness, protection of the vulnerable, or emotional concern for characters’ well-being. Reviewers may praise films for being touching, compassionate, or emotionally moving.
Equality	Equality captures the belief that all collective identities should be treated the same, with equal rights, opportunities, and outcomes.	Equality is reflected in narratives or evaluations that stress fairness, social justice, levelling hierarchies, or equal treatment across groups. Reviewers may emphasize themes of inclusivity, fairness, or solidarity against discrimination.
Proportionality	Proportionality reflects fairness based on merit, contribution, or deservingness—rewards and punishments should match effort and responsibility.	Proportionality shows up in stories or judgments about meritocracy, justice served, or characters getting what they deserve. Reviewers may comment on satisfying endings where effort is

		rewarded, wrongdoers punished, or balance restored.
Loyalty-betrayal	Loyalty emphasizes allegiance to one’s group, community, or nation, and the virtue of standing by one’s side.	Loyalty is expressed in narratives about friendship, family bonds, patriotism, or group cohesion. Reviewers may highlight the value of commitment, betrayal, or solidarity in their evaluation of the film.
Authority-subversion	Authority involves respect for tradition, leadership, and hierarchical social structures. It reflects the virtue of obedience and deference to legitimate roles.	Authority is present in narratives about order, respect, tradition, or strong leaders. Reviewers may praise (or criticize) depictions of respect for rules, parental or political authority, and the consequences of defying hierarchy.
Sanctity-purity	Purity is grounded in concerns about sanctity, cleanliness, and protection from degradation, often tied to sexuality, the body, or the sacred.	Purity appears in narratives dealing with innocence, taboo, corruption, or moral ‘contamination’. Reviewers may highlight how a film provokes disgust, addresses sacred values, portrays innocence, or pushes boundaries of decency.

Table 2. *Specification of the MF (Moral Foundations) dimension.*

7.1.2 Motivational Orientation

Our **Motivational Orientation** dimension (two variables: **Hedonic** and **Eudaimonic**) is consistent with a major line of entertainment theory that explains media selection and reception as forms of **affect regulation** and **gratification seeking**. Mood Management Theory (MMT) proposes that people tend to select media that helps optimize their current affective state (maximize pleasant feeling, minimize unpleasant feeling). Subsequent work, including **mood adjustment** accounts, explicitly addresses departures from simple hedonism (e.g., purposeful selection of negative or challenging content for catharsis, meaning-making, or other utilities),

and highlights how individual differences and situational constraints shape these choices (Zillmann, 1988; Knobloch, 2003; Knobloch-Westerwick & Alter, 2006).

Entertainment research has converged on a distinction between hedonic motivations (pleasure seeking, fun, relaxation, diversion) and eudaimonic motivations (truth-seeking, insight, reflection, and ‘appreciation’ rather than simple enjoyment), with the latter capturing experiences that audiences describe as meaningful, moving, or important even when they are not pleasant in a narrow sense (Oliver & Raney, 2011).

In this perspective, **Motivational Orientation is not a property of the film alone but of the viewing experience as described by audiences**: CineFlux treats hedonic and eudaimonic orientations as dimensions of how reviewers frame what they sought and what they valued in watching a film. In other words, here the reviewer speaks about themselves.

Variable	Definition (in psychology)	In film reviews
Hedonic pathway	In psychology, hedonism refers to selecting and using media to maximize pleasure, fun, and positive affect —regulating mood toward enjoyment, amusement, and excitement (e.g., ‘mood management’, light-hearted play).	In reviews, hedonic entertainment is framed as fun-first : the film is ‘a blast’ ‘hilarious’, ‘pure entertainment’, ‘never boring’, ‘feel-good’, ‘crowd-pleasing’ or great ‘escapism’. Comments prioritize amusement, laughter, thrills, energy, and an enjoyable pace over depth or reflection.
Eudaimonic pathway	In psychology, eudaimonia captures truth-/meaning-seeking motivations:	In reviews, eudaimonic entertainment is described as meaningful or thought-

	<p>using media to reflect, contemplate life’s purpose, and gain insight into the human condition. The affect profile often includes mixed emotions (e.g., feeling moved, compassionate, inspired, or saddened) and aligns with “appreciation” rather than simple enjoyment.</p>	<p>provoking: the film questions assumptions, presents moral dilemmas, explores love, loss, mortality, injustice, dignity, or a search for identity/purpose, and invites reflection. Reviewers note being moved, inspired, contemplative, or that the film offers profound themes/messages—even if it isn’t ‘fun’ in the hedonic sense.</p>
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Table 3. *Specification of MO (Motivational Orientation) dimension (pathways)*

The hierarchical structure of the MO dimension (see Table 3) is more complex than that of MF because MO has two pathways (hedonic and eudaimonic), each with distinct variables. For the **hedonic pathway** CineFlux considers the following variables,

1. **Humour - amusement**: The reviewer mentions humour/comedy efficacy as part of their enjoyment (laughter, jokes landing, comic relief working).
2. **Thrill - arousal**: The reviewer mentions excitement/arousal (thrill, adrenaline, edge-of-seat stimulation) as part of enjoyment.
3. **Comfort - mood - regulation**: The reviewer frames the film as serving **comfort, relaxation, switching-off, soothing, or mood improvement** (including ‘feel-good’ uplift) as a viewing goal/outcome.
4. **Hedonic - generic**: The reviewer expresses a **general hedonic reception appraisal** (entertainment/pleasure/diversion/escapism/enjoyment) that is **not specific enough** to be confidently classified as any of the above.

In our implementation, eudaimonic responses are further differentiated into reflection (the experience ‘stays with’ the viewer and prompts ongoing thought), insight (the viewer reports gaining new understanding about moral, existential, or social issues), and meaning-appreciation

(the viewer explicitly frames the film as important, profound, or humanly significant), more specifically,

1. **Reflection-rumination**: The reviewer reports reflective uptake: lingering thoughts, contemplation, rumination, “stayed with me”, “made me reflect”.
2. **Insight-illumination**: The reviewer claims the film provides genuine insight/illumination (existential, philosophical, or psychological).
3. **Meaning-appreciation**: The reviewer frames the experience as valuable because of explicit **existential or human significance** (purpose/identity/redemption; core human conditions like loss/mortality/dignity/injustice) and/or **meaning-laden affect** (awe, elevation, solemn appreciation) presented as worthwhile.
4. **Eudaimonic-generic**: The reviewer expresses a **general eudaimonic reception appraisal** (meaningful/worthwhile/important/deep/moving in a deeper sense) that is **not specific enough** to be confidently classified as any of the above.

Within CineFlux, hedonic and eudaimonic pathways thus provide an interpretable map of how audiences describe the *kind* of value a film delivered—whether it was primarily ‘a good time’, a meaningful confrontation with difficult themes, or a mixture of both.

7.2 Model operationalization

CineFlux treats reviews as evaluative discourse. When a reviewer writes about a film, they do not merely describe events; they perform speech acts, positioning themselves with respect to content and norms (Austin, 1962; Du Bois, 2007; Martin & White, 2005). We designed a marker architecture that operationalizes this by asking, for each variable, whether the review signals that the variable is at stake (**trigger**), provides a concrete account realizing it (**appraisal**), and takes an evaluative position toward it (**stance**).

The CineFlux marker architecture operationalizes this idea in a simple, reusable pattern. For any variable in the model—whether a Moral Foundation or a Motivational Orientation—it asks three questions of the review text:

1. **Q1: trigger:** Has the reviewer indicated that this variable is at stake at all?
2. **Q2: appraisal:** Have they provided concrete, text-grounded evidence or an account that realises it?
3. **Q3: stance:** Have they taken an evaluative position towards how it manifests in the film or in their experience of it?

Each marker is implemented as an extractive, evidence-linked decision: the model does not simply label a review; it identifies the precise span of text that indicates a trigger, that realizes an appraisal, or that encodes stance (as further explained in §7.3). This speech-act framing enables CineFlux to represent reception in a way that is both theoretically grounded and auditable: stakeholders can see not only *what* was inferred but also *how* the inference is anchored in the input reviews.

The same three-marker template is then specialized for each dimension: in Moral Foundations, markers are anchored to story-world entities and events; in Motivational Orientation, they are anchored to the viewer’s reported experience.

7.2.1 Operationalizing moral foundations

Why post-consumption review text remains aligned with MF?

Moral Foundations Theory is not restricted to pre-consumption choice; it is a theory of moral cognition that describes how people detect morally relevant cues, appraise them, and form judgements when they encounter them (Graham et al., 2009, 2013). CineFlux applies this logic to reception. Reviews frequently contain: (i) identification of morally relevant material in the

story world (what happened, which norms or relationships were implicated); (ii) appraisals of that material (why it is framed as harmful, unfair, disloyal, subversive, sacred, etc.); and (iii) stances towards the film's handling of it. Our operationalization therefore remains theoretically consistent: it captures the moral *reading* of the narrative. As previously mentioned, MF in CineFlux is always about the story world as discussed by the reviewer; it is not a model of the reviewer's personal moral character or ideology.

Mapping the three markers to story-world moral reception.

For each MF variable (care-harm, equality, proportionality, loyalty-betrayal, authority-subversion, sanctity-purity), CineFlux applies the Trigger-Appraisal-Stance model as follows:

Trigger identified (foundation cue) asks whether the reviewer indicates that a given foundation is at stake in the narrative. This includes explicit naming (“the film is about injustice”, “a betrayal of trust”) and implicit cues where the review clearly frames events in care, fairness, loyalty, authority or purity terms, even without detailed description.

Appraisal expression (story-world evidence) asks whether the review provides a concrete, narrative-anchored account that realizes the foundation: an act of harm or protection; a pattern of equal or unequal treatment; deservingness and proportionality of rewards and punishments; instances of loyalty or betrayal; acceptance or defiance of authority; motifs of contamination, taboo, or sanctity. Requiring such evidence prevents the model from firing on generic moralized rhetoric, political slogans, or vague outrage that is not actually tied to what the film depicts.

Stance (evaluation of the film's treatment of the moral element) asks how the reviewer positions themselves relative to the moral pattern they have identified and appraised. The same foundation can appear in opposed stances: a reviewer may praise a film for exposing injustice, condemn it for glamorizing cruelty, or dismiss a moral message as heavy-handed or incoherent.

Stance thus captures whether the film’s moral handling is endorsed, rejected, or problematized, not merely whether the theme is present.

Handling polarized moral disagreement.

In polarized environments, it is easy to conflate moral content with political alignment. The separation between trigger and appraisal prevents this collapse: the system can register that a foundation is invoked, but it counts it as an expressed appraisal only when the reviewer links it to specific story-world evidence. The separation between appraisal and stance then captures a common pattern in contentious titles: reviewers may agree on what morally relevant events occur in the film, yet diverge on whether the film treats them responsibly (Cantone et al., 2025; Day & Kim, 2023). The MF outputs, therefore, stay conservative and descriptively faithful since they describe how the narrative is morally read, not which side the reviewer is ‘on’.

Interpretability for analysis and decision-support.

Because each MF variable marker is linked to an extractive quote span (as explained later in §7.3), stakeholders can inspect, for any film or audience segment, which passages of text supported a care-harm trigger, which sentences articulated an equality or proportionality appraisal, and how stances divided. This makes moral reception patterns inspectable and defensible: aggregate MF scores can always be traced back to specific evaluative speech acts in the corpus.

7.2.2 Operationalizing motivational orientation

Why post-consumption review text remains aligned with MO?

The theories underpinning Motivational Orientation often focus on selection—how people choose media under particular moods—but they also emphasize how audiences *report* what media did for them—what gratifications it provided, what states it helped them reach, what

kinds of value they derived (Zillmann, 1988; Oliver & Raney, 2011). CineFlux operates on this reception side. Reviews routinely contain retrospective accounts (“this was exactly what I needed after a long day”, “it left me thinking about it for weeks”) and explicit evaluations of whether the experience was worthwhile. We therefore do not infer pre-watch mood. Instead, we extract the reviewer’s self-reported motivational orientation and appraisal—hedonic or eudaimonic, or a mixture—as expressed in language.

Mapping the three markers to hedonic and eudaimonic reception.

For Motivational Orientation, the same trigger–appraisal–stance pattern is applied, but the scope is the viewer’s experience rather than the story world.

Trigger identified (orientation framing) asks whether the reviewer frames the experience in hedonic or eudaimonic terms at all. Hedonic triggers include descriptions of the film as “pure fun”, “escapist entertainment”, “a good laugh”, or “perfect background movie”. Eudaimonic triggers include frames such as “thought-provoking”, “moving”, “important”, “made me think differently”, or “not exactly fun, but...”. This captures the broad orientation even when the account is brief.

Appraisal expression (viewer reception cue) asks whether the reviewer articulates a concrete, experiential account consistent with a hedonic or eudaimonic pathway. Hedonic appraisals include self-reports of amusement, excitement, relaxation, comfort, or mood improvement (“I laughed all the way through”, “it helped me switch off”). Eudaimonic appraisals include reports of reflection, insight, or meaning-laden appreciation (“it stayed with me”, “it made me reconsider...”, “it captures something true about grief”). Requiring such appraisals prevents over-firing on isolated adjectives (“deep”, “fun”) that appear without a clear motivational frame.

Stance (pathway appraisal) asks how the reviewer evaluates the pathway itself. A hedonic experience can be endorsed (“exactly the kind of mindless fun I wanted”) or criticized (“just dumb fun with nothing to say”). Likewise, a eudaimonic attempt can be welcomed (“it really made me reflect”) or rejected (“it tries too hard to be profound”). This reflects the fact that mood-management and appreciation theories recognize that gratifications are filtered through self-control goals, identity, and situational fit (Knobloch, 2003; Knobloch-Westerwick & Alter, 2006; Oliver & Raney, 2011).

Handling non-hedonic negative content.

A common challenge for simplistic hedonism is that people sometimes seek sad, frightening, or morally uncomfortable films. Mood-adjustment and appreciation accounts treat such choices as functional: negative affect can be part of a valued experience if it serves reflection, catharsis, or meaning-making. CineFlux’s MO implementation is compatible with this view because it does not equate hedonic with “positive emotion” or eudaimonic with “negative emotion”. Instead, it reads the reviewer’s articulated orientation and stance. The same sadness can appear as an unwanted burden (“just depressing”) or as a meaningful, appreciated experience (“sad but beautiful”), and the stance marker distinguishes these cases.

Interpretability for analysis and decision-support.

As with MF, every MO decision is tied to an evidence span. Analysts can see, for a given film or audience segment, which phrases indicate that viewers treated the film as comfort, distraction, thrill, reflection, insight, or deep appreciation, and how often each pathway was endorsed or rejected. This allows dashboards and reports to distinguish ‘what kind of value the film tended to deliver’ from ‘how that value was judged’, using a small, interpretable set of reception speech acts derived systematically from review language.

7.3 LLM prompt design for review annotation

7.3.1 Overview of the prompting approach

This section specifies how the marker architecture introduced in §7.2 is implemented using LLM-based prompts.

As described in the previous section, the CineFlux pipeline employs a canonical, speech-act guided architecture, whose goal is to extract audience-reception signals from film reviews in a way that is auditable, theory-aligned, and scalable across model dimensions. We rely on advanced large language models (LLMs) with data-annotation capabilities to implement this architecture (Tan et al., 2024).

Early iterations of the data annotation pipeline relied on sentence-level tagging, i.e., asking the LLM to decide, sentence by sentence, whether a marker (e.g. trigger) was present. That approach proved brittle because it encouraged boundary errors, inflated false positives, and ignored the fact that many reception cues (moral judgements, appraisals, implied alignments) are expressed across the full review rather than in isolated sentences.

For the CineFlux MVP we therefore adopted a global-reading protocol. For each target variable, the model reads the entire review and then answers a small, fixed sequence of questions, each corresponding to one of our reception-relevant speech act markers. This design choice treats language as action and evaluation as a structured set of linguistic resources, rather than a bag of keywords (Austin, 1962; Martin & White, 2005).

The canonical prompts and variable specifications were not fixed in a single design step. They were refined through several annotation cycles in which random samples of reviews were manually coded by the research team and compared with model outputs. Disagreements were analysed to adjust the discriminant logics (`Y_LOGIC`), appraisal cue-sets (`Y_APPRAISAL_TERMS`), and stance rules (`Y_STANCE_DEFINITIONS`), with particular

attention to borderline cases (e.g. plot summaries with weak evaluation, morally charged language without story-world anchoring, or ambiguous hedonic/eudaimonic framings). These cycles continued until model decisions on held-out samples were judged to be conservative and theory-consistent, and until the evidence spans returned by the model could reliably be used as training material for new annotators. This iterative procedure ensured that the final prompting regime is anchored in concrete annotation practice rather than only in abstract construct definitions.

The aim is not generic sentiment analysis. CineFlux is a theory-grounded reception model that extracts evidence that a review expresses specific constructs, each defined by an explicit psychological dimension and operationalized through discriminant logic, appraisal cues, and stance rules. As previously explained, the CineFlux MVP focuses on two dimensions: (i) Moral Foundations Theory (MF) and (ii) entertainment-gratification work, distinguishing hedonic versus eudaimonic orientations (MO). The rationale for this reduction in the MVP is described in §7.1. However, the full working model considered five dimensions (see SI WP73-A-01).

A second critical design driver is traceability for stakeholders in an EU policy use case. Each inferred marker must be verifiable in the source review text. Each decision is therefore returned with a discrete label and an extractive evidence span (a verbatim quote plus character indices), along with minimal justification from the backend model. This aligns with interpretability work that operationalizes explanations as extractive rationales and evaluates their faithfulness (DeYoung et al., 2020).

7.3.2 Canonical model structure

Canonical parameterization: what the prompt ‘knows’. The canonical prompt is instantiated by a small set of parameters, split across dimension-level and variable-level definitions.

1. **X (Dimension name) and X_SCOPE (scope constraint).** X identifies the dimension's theoretical grounding (e.g., moral-foundations vs motivational-orientation). X_SCOPE determines what counts as admissible evidence:
 - a. **STORY_WORLD:** evidence must concern entities/events/actions in the film's narrative world (characters, groups, institutions).
 - b. **REVIEWER_EXPERIENCE:** evidence must concern the reviewer's experienced gratification or engagement mode (pleasure, relaxation, reflection, meaning), as expressed in the review text (Oliver & Raney, 2011).
2. **Y (Variable name).** Y identifies a variable within the chosen dimension, e.g., care-harm and equality are variables in the Moral Foundations dimension.
3. **Y_LOGIC (discriminant logic).** Y_LOGIC states, in theory terms, what counts as linguistic evidence that variable Y is present. This is the primary guardrail against category drift. In MF, Y_LOGIC is grounded in Moral Foundations Theory definitions (e.g., care/harm vs loyalty/betrayal vs authority/subversion; and equality vs proportionality as distinct fairness intuitions). In MO, Y_LOGIC anchors the hedonic/eudaimonic distinction to reception language about gratification and appreciation (Oliver & Raney, 2011).
4. **Y_APPRAISAL_TERMS (appraisal-expression cues).** These are lexical and pragmatic cues indicating that the reviewer is not merely mentioning Y_LOGIC, but expressing an appraisal–evaluation, endorsement, rejection, satisfaction, contempt, obligation language, and related stance-bearing resources. This component is grounded in discourse-analytic work on evaluative language and appraisal (Martin & White, 2005).
5. **Y_STANCE_DEFINITIONS (variable-specific stance rules).** The stance labels are shared across the system (positive/negative/neutral/unclear/None), but their meaning

is variable-relative. “Positive” for care–harm in MF concerns alignment with protecting vulnerable entities, whereas “positive” for proportionality (also MF) concerns approval of deserved outcomes. This follows the stance-taking view that evaluation is an act of positioning that must be interpreted relative to the object of evaluation (Du Bois, 2007).

7.3.3 Canonical inference

Each variable, *Y*, is inferred via the same three-marker sequence. The structure decomposes a complex judgement into controlled intermediate outputs, while preserving full-review context.

Q1. Trigger identified (presence of Y_LOGIC). This is a strict YES/NO gate that asks whether the review contains admissible evidence for *Y_LOGIC* under *X_SCOPE*. The purpose is anchoring. It ties the review to the variable *Y*’s construct without yet committing to evaluation.

Q2. Appraisal expression. This is the reception-relevant marker. It detects whether the reviewer expresses a concrete appraisal tied to *Y*–approval/condemnation, endorsement/rejection, obligation language, satisfaction, disappointment, or, for MO, explicit reception claims about the viewing mode (“relaxing and fun”, “escapist”, “stayed with me”, “made me reflect”). The cue-set *Y_APPRAISAL_TERMS* constrains this marker so it does not over-fire on vague descriptors that appear without a reception claim (Martin & White, 2005; Oliver & Raney, 2011).

Q3. Stance (variable-relative orientation). Stance assigns positive, negative, neutral, unclear or None using *Y_STANCE_DEFINITIONS*, grounded in the same admissible evidence span. This matters because the same construct can be present yet evaluated negatively (e.g., “mindless fun” as criticism; “tries to be profound” as dismissal). The system treats stance as a variable-relative operation, not as generic sentiment (Du Bois, 2007).

Externalized reasoning requirement (evidence + minimal justification). For Q1–Q3 the output must include: (i) the label (YES/NO or stance), (ii) a one-sentence justification, (iii) a

verbatim quote, and (iv) character indices (`[char_start, char_end]`). The intention is not to elicit free-form chain-of-thought, but to output auditable grounds in the form of extractive evidence, consistent with rationale-based interpretability approaches (DeYoung et al., 2020; Lei et al., 2016). Chain-of-thought prompting can improve performance on some reasoning tasks (Kojima et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2022), but explanation text can be plausible while unfaithful to the true drivers of the answer because the LLM is making inferences (Turpin et al., 2023). CineFlux therefore constrains ‘explanation’ to an extractive evidence span plus a minimal justification that directly references that span, in line with calls to distinguish persuasive rationalization from faithful explanation (Jacovi & Goldberg, 2020).

Canonical reuse and modularity. Operationally, the system runs one prompt per variable Y , rather than multi-label tagging in a single pass. This design reduces cross-variable interference, makes semantic boundaries easier to maintain, and avoids score inflation when later aggregating Y -level markers into dimension scores. It also follows a broader pattern in LLM systems design: complex behaviour becomes more controllable when built from small, inspectable steps rather than a single monolithic call (Wu et al., 2022). However, controlling semantic bleed between variables this way comes with increased costs when using commercial LLMs (as we do here).

Within the parameterization, the LLM executes the same canonical sequence:

1. **Trigger identified** (YES/NO): anchors the review to Y under X_SCOPE using Y_LOGIC .
2. **Appraisal expression** (YES/NO): detects reception-relevant appraisal tied to Y , grounded in $Y_APPRAISAL_TERMS$.
3. **Stance classification** (positive/negative/neutral/unclear/None): assigns stance using $Y_STANCE_DEFINITIONS$, grounded in the same evidence span.

4. **Evidence extraction and indexing:** returns a verbatim quote plus (`[char_start, char_end]`) indices for deterministic auditing.
5. **JSON-structured output:** returns a strictly validated JSON object with fixed keys, enabling automated parsing and aggregation.

Why is this canonical across dimensions despite different scopes? Because the architecture is identical, only `X_SCOPE` changes what counts as admissible evidence.

- a. **MF (STORY_WORLD):** detects morally salient story events/conditions and the reviewer's appraisal of them.
- b. **MO (REVIEWER_EXPERIENCE):** detects the reviewer's expressed gratification mode (hedonic vs eudaimonic) and their appraisal of that mode (Oliver & Raney, 2011).

The pipeline's core properties are:

- a. **Transparency:** every decision is anchored to a quote span with indices.
- b. **Reproducibility:** the same variable always triggers the same question sequence and schema.
- c. **Modularity:** each variable is processed independently, limiting interference and overlap.
- d. **Robustness to drift:** the model is constrained by pre-specified logics and stance rules rather than open-ended classification.

Externalized inference as a design choice. A core design principle in the CineFlux MVP is that LLM outputs must be externally auditable. An explicit decision, a minimal justification, and an extractive evidence span with character indices accompany each inferred marker. The system treats the quotation span as the primary explanation object, and the justification as a

minimal linking statement. This reduces the space for confabulated explanation text and makes quality control tractable at scale (DeYoung et al., 2020; Turpin et al., 2023).

Implications for scoring and deliverable auditability. Because markers are explicit and evidence-backed, the MVP can compute deterministic variable- and dimension-level scores from stored intermediate outputs, while preserving a trace back to the original text. This directly supports:

1. **Traceability:** every score can be reconstructed from stored marker decisions and evidence spans.
2. **Debuggability:** errors can be localized to trigger vs appraisal vs stance.
3. **Controlled generalization:** decomposition reduces drift when scaling to many variables and large corpora (Wei et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2022).

Why does this yield strong LLM performance in practice? The performance gain does not come from assumed LLM inference capacity. It comes from disciplined constraints. Global interpretation reduces sentence-level noise: the model must interpret the review as a whole before answering any question. This matters because moral evaluations and reception appraisals are frequently indirect, discourse-level, and context-dependent. Constrained decision boundaries reduce over-interpretation: YES/NO framing makes the model more cautious and less speculative, especially when coupled with an evidence requirement (DeYoung et al., 2020). Where early prompting strategies encouraged hallucinated or over-extended inferences, the constrained architecture only permits commitments that can be supported explicitly in the text. Discriminant logic reduces semantic bleed: **Y_LOGIC** defines what counts as evidence for Y in the current run. In MF, this protects distinctions such as equality vs proportionality (Atari et al., 2023). In MO, it separates hedonic enjoyment cues from eudaimonic appreciation cues (Freytag et al., 2024). JSON schema contracts reduce output

drift: a strict output format reduces uncontrolled generation and allows automated validation, aggregation, and monitoring.

The role of negative filters (scope enforcement, not cosmetic rules). Negative filters prevent the model drifting into film criticism or generic sentiment, and they operationalize X_SCOPE as an enforceable constraint.

Under **STORY_WORLD**, the model ignores references that concern only the reviewer’s personal emotions or preferences, film quality, or general mood/atmosphere that are not tied to what happens to entities in the plot. It keeps only references that concern characters, groups, institutions, or plot-relevant conditions and where the judgement is directed at those entities/actions/conditions. A consistency check guides this: “Is this about what happens to entities in the plot, not about my viewing experience?”

Under **REVIEWER_EXPERIENCE**, the model ignores plot-only summaries with no motivational framing or reception claim, as well as purely technical film critique unless explicitly tied to the motivational pathway. It keeps only text in which the reviewer describes viewing orientation, preference, satisfaction, or engagement mode, and where the language indicates hedonic enjoyment/escapism or eudaimonic appreciation/meaning. The consistency check is: “Is this about what the film did for the viewer (pleasure vs meaning), not moral evaluation of plot events?”

7.3.4 Inference methodology (LLM prompting paradigms used)

To ensure reliable annotation of moral- and value-relevant reception signals, the CineFlux MVP combines:

- a. **Zero-shot reasoning prompts** for global interpretation and controlled inference decomposition (Kojima et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2022).

- b. **Constrained instruction-following patterns** aligned with instruction-tuned models and safety-oriented alignment work (Bai et al., 2022; Ouyang et al., 2022).
- c. **Evidence-anchored verification** behaviours that favour conservative, text-grounded outputs over unconstrained rationalization (DeYoung et al., 2020; Maynez et al., 2020; Turpin et al., 2023).

The core inference is run in a zero-shot regime; few-shot exemplars are not required in production and, where used in experimentation, serve reliability and error isolation rather than adding new classification degrees of freedom (Madaan et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022).

Independent inference per variable (conceptual separation and score integrity). Each variable in the model is inferred independently, using its own dedicated prompt instantiation. This design choice follows directly from the canonical architecture: every run loads a single discriminant definition (`Y_LOGIC`), a single cue-set for appraisal expression (`Y_APPRAISAL_TERMS`), and a single set of stance rules (`Y_STANCE_DEFINITIONS`), all under an explicit scope constraint (`X_SCOPE`). In contrast, a multi-variable prompt asks the model to apply several competing discriminant definitions simultaneously. In our testing, that is precisely the condition under which semantic bleed, stance confusion, and over-classification become likely, because the model can satisfy ‘some’ variable logic somewhere in the text and then generalize that evidence across variables that should remain distinct.

The one-variable-per-call design protects both conceptual separation and score integrity. It prevents double-counting when downstream scoring aggregates variable outputs into dimension scores, and it makes failures diagnosable: when performance drops, the error can be localized to a specific variable definition, cue-set, stance rule, or scope filter rather than being entangled with other variables.

The design has direct methodological and operational benefits: robustness improves because errors remain local to one variable rather than propagating across the annotation set. Interpretability improves because each output is a focused, evidence-grounded decision trace aligned with one construct definition. Conceptual purity improves because the discriminant logic stays uncontaminated by neighbouring constructs. Scalability improves because adding variables does not require redesigning the protocol; it requires only adding a new variable specification under the same template. Parallelization becomes straightforward because variables are independent compute units. Accountability improves because the inference remains constrained, auditable, and resistant to speculative interpretation, which is a practical requirement in EU evaluation settings.

Fit with the Crescine MVP and the wider multi-dimensional model. This canonical prompting architecture is the enabling layer for the MVP. It produces interpretable markers that downstream teams (saturation, scoring, analytics, dashboarding) can rely on as structurally consistent and replicable. It also supports standardization across EU countries and languages because every variable is operationalized through the same protocol; only the theory-specific definitions change.

Because each dimension in the full model reuses the same trigger → appraisal expression → stance sequence under a defined scope, the overall audience model remains modular and composable. Visualization and comparison across corpora becomes substantially easier, and the pipeline remains interpretable for film-funding and policy stakeholders—an explicit requirement of Crescine deliverables.

Summary. The prompting approach is a theory-aligned annotation protocol engineered for audience reception modelling at scale. It separates (i) construct anchoring via discriminant logic, (ii) reception-relevant appraisal expression, and (iii) stance as a variable-relative qualifier. It enforces scope through negative filters, requires evidence-linked outputs, and preserves a

stable JSON contract for aggregation and audit. The system is not a set of ad-hoc prompts; it is a canonical, parameterized, evidence-constrained method consistent with linguistic accounts of evaluation and stance (Austin, 1962; Martin & White, 2005; Du Bois, 2007) and with interpretability work that treats rationales as inspectable evidence objects (Lei et al., 2016; DeYoung et al., 2020), while explicitly mitigating known risks of unfaithful explanation text (Turpin et al., 2023; Jacovi & Goldberg, 2020).

7.4 From AI review annotation to quantified audience variables

As described previously, CineFlux represents each theoretical variable, y , in the audience model (e.g., `care-harm`; `hedonic_fun_amusement`) using a canonical annotation object with three LLM-generated outputs: (i) an **in-scope trigger decision** (Q1), (ii) an **appraisal-expression decision** (Q2), and (iii) a **reviewer-stance label** (Q3). Each output is grounded in an extractive evidence span (a verbatim quote with character indices), so that subsequent quantification remains auditable. The pipeline then converts these qualitative outputs into numeric values that can be aggregated consistently across reviews, films, audience segments, as well as production or market countries. This conversion is required because CineFlux treats each review as a point in a d -dimensional feature space, where, d , equals the total number of model variables (six MF plus eight MO for a total of 14 in the current design) and the core tool functions depend on numerical operations, most importantly, computing similarity (or distance) between reviews to support clustering, comparison, and 2D visual projection. These requirements warrant a deterministic mapping from canonical annotation objects to review-level quantitative vectors.

7.4.1 Canonical outputs (per variable, per review)

For a given review, r , and variable, y , the LLM returns three outputs.

First, **Trigger identified**, $t_{r,y} \in \{0,1\}$. The value $t_{r,y} = 1$ holds only when the review contains admissible evidence for the variable’s discriminant definition (Y_LOGIC) under the relevant scope (X_SCOPE).

Second, **Appraisal expressed**, $a_{r,y} \in \{0,1\}$. The value $a_{r,y} = 1$ holds only when the review contains an explicit evaluative or commitment speech act about the same in-scope target, consistent with $Y_APPRAISAL_TERMS$.

Third, **Reviewer stance**. The stance label $s_{r,y} \in \{\text{positive, negative, neutral, unclear, None}\}$ is interpreted using $Y_STANCE_DEFINITIONS$, which defines the meaning of ‘positive’ and ‘negative’ relative to the variable’s discriminant logic, rather than generic sentiment.

The prompting protocol imposes monotonic dependence between markers. Appraisal presupposes an in-scope trigger: $a_{r,y} = 1 \Rightarrow t_{r,y} = 1$. Directional stance presupposes an expressed appraisal: $s_{r,y} \in \{\text{positive, negative}\} \Rightarrow a_{r,y} = 1$. Where $t_{r,y} = 1$, and $a_{r,y} = 0$, stance is restricted to neutral or unclear (depending on evidential clarity), rather than positive or negative. These constraints reduce false positives and prevent the scoring layer from treating vague mentions as evidence of reception.

7.4.2 Review x Variable scoring

CineFlux converts the LLM output annotations for each review x variable, (r, y) , pair into two numeric values. The first is variable’s **activation**, $\alpha_{r,y} \in [0,1]$. This measures how strongly the variable is present in the review, regardless of (stance) direction. Recall that for each variable, y , there is a binary marker triplet, $(t_{r,y}, a_{r,y}, \delta_{r,y})$, where $\delta_{r,y} = 1 \Rightarrow s_{r,y} \in \{\text{positive, negative}\}$, otherwise, 0.

We defined a weight mapping triplet (w_t, w_a, w_δ) that allows CineFlux to configure the contribution each within variable marker, m , has on the variable’s activation.

$$\alpha_{r,y} = w_t t_{r,y} + w_a a_{r,y} + w_s \delta_{r,y}$$

For example, if for a given pair, (r, y) , the marker triplet is, $(1, 1, 0)$, and the weights are, $(0.2, 0.4, 0.4)$, then the variable activation is,

$$\alpha_{r,y} = 0.2 \times 1 + 0.4 \times 1 + 0.4 \times 0 = 0.6$$

For variable activation, positive and negative stances contribute equally since activation quantifies the stance's directional magnitude, but not the direction itself—this equal contribution is captured by $\delta_{r,y}$. A (complementary) second measure, the variable's **signed orientation**, $\sigma_{r,y} \in [-1,1]$, measures directional leaning for the variable by taking the magnitude implied by the evidence when the reviewer expresses a positive or negative stance, and it is zero when the reviewer's stance is neutral, unclear, or absent.

In other words, $\alpha_{r,y}$ captures *how much* the variable is evidenced, whereas, $\sigma_{r,y}$ captures *which way* the evidence leans when a directional stance is present.

The formula for signed orientation is identical to that of activation. The only difference is that while in activation the stance weight is always multiplied by $\delta = 1$ (both when stance is positive or negative), signed orientation multiplies by $\tau = 1$ when stance is positive, and by $\tau = -1$ when stance is negative. For further mathematical details on both the activation and signed-orientation measures, see SI WP73-C-01.

Weights are treated as system parameters (recorded under *pipeline*, alongside the schema version, see §6.3) so that (a) the user can adjust them, and (b) downstream scores remain fully reproducible and auditable.

7.4.3 Review vectors

Computing activation and signed orientation for, e.g., all variables $\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{Y}^x$ for a given review, \mathbf{r} , results in its fixed-length vector representation based on the audience model and its assumptions. We denote these vectors by, $\alpha_{\mathbf{r}}^x$ (activation) and $\sigma_{\mathbf{r}}^x$ (signed orientation).

For **moral foundations (MF)**, the vector components correspond to MF variables in the following order:

1. Care-harm
2. Equality
3. Proportionality
4. Loyalty-betrayal
5. Authority-subversion
6. Sanctity-purity

For the **hedonic pathway** in **motivational orientation (MO)**,

1. Humour-amusement
2. Thrill-arousal
3. Comfort-mood-regulation
4. Hedonic-generic

Finally, for the **eudaimonic pathway** in **motivational orientation (MO)**,

1. Reflection-rumination
2. Insight-illumination
3. Meaning-appreciation
4. Eudaimonic-general

Note: this is the same order in which dimensional variables were introduced in §7.1.

This design supports downstream projection (e.g., 2D embedding) and consistent film- and segment-level comparisons without score inflation from overlapping prompts, since each variable is inferred independently.

7.4.4 Film- and segment-level aggregation

CineFlux does not treat an individual review as a definitive statement about a film’s audience reception. Instead, it treats each **review as its analysis unit**. We have explained how a review is first described in terms of the CineFlux audience model (through LLM-based annotation). From an annotated review, we take a further step to compute activation and signed orientation. The true power of these measures lies in their calculation for a clearly defined set of reviews. This aggregation step turns review-level annotations into stakeholder-facing evidence on films, audience segments, and cross-country patterns.

Cohorts as the unit of aggregation. All reported scores are computed over a review subset \mathcal{C} , a ‘cohort’ obtained from a specific, audience-relevant subset of reviews defined by a query. In the simplest case, $\mathcal{C} = \mathcal{R}_f$, is the set of all reviews for film, f . In other cases, \mathcal{C} , may denote only the public reviews for, f , only the reviews for, f , produced by a particular segmented audience $a_i \in \mathcal{A}$, or a segment-defined cohort spanning multiple films. This single notation allows the same scoring logic to be applied consistently across films, public baselines, focus-group segments, countries, and time windows. The formal definition of cohorts and the indexing conventions are provided in SI WP73-C-01 §1.

Central cohort measurements. For each variable, y , in a given dimension \mathbf{X} , CineFlux first computes two cohort summaries. The first is the **mean activation**, $\bar{\alpha}_{\mathcal{C},y}$. For any cohort of reviews \mathcal{C} (e.g., all reviews for a film; public reviews only; a specific audience segment), CineFlux reports two complementary summaries per variable, y :

$$\bar{\alpha}_{c,y} = \frac{1}{n_c} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{C}} \alpha_{r,y} \in [0,1]$$

This quantity captures **how present the variable is in the cohort's reviews**, independent of whether the stance is positive or negative. In practical terms, $\bar{\alpha}_{c,y}$, measures how present is, y , in that cohort.

The second is the **mean stance orientation**, $\bar{\sigma}_{c,y}$, (positive versus negative) about that variable,

$$\bar{\sigma}_{c,y} = \frac{1}{n_c} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{C}} \sigma_{r,y} \in [-1,1]$$

This quantity captures **net leaning**: positive and negative contributions cancel, and the residual indicates the cohort's overall directional stance for, y , (and, when aggregated across variables, for a dimension). It answers 'which way does the cohort lean, on balance?', not 'how much stance is present?'

The third is the **proportion of directional stance** (i.e. the proportion of reviews that have positive or negative stance),

$$\bar{\rho}_{c,y} = \frac{1}{n_c} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{C}} |\sigma_{r,y}| \in [0,1]$$

Note that this is the fraction of reviews in, \mathcal{C} , where the model assigns a *directional* stance (positive or negative) for y . This measure disambiguates situations where, $\bar{\sigma} \approx 0$, is due to polarized cancellation from those where this quantity is close to zero because most reviews have a neutral/unclear stance.

These per-variable means are the core diagnostic layer: they let the analyst see which constructs are actually driving a film’s reception profile, rather than presenting only a single aggregate number.

Dimension-level aggregates. Stakeholders often need a compact summary per dimension (e.g., ‘moral content is salient’ or ‘hedonic pathway dominates’) without losing comparability. CineFlux therefore computes a dimension-level aggregated activation score A_X^C by taking a normalized mean over the variables in that dimension. Normalization by d_X (the number of variables in X) ensures that dimension scores remain comparable even when dimensions contain different numbers of variables. In parallel, CineFlux computes a dimension-level aggregated signed orientation O_X^C , which summarizes whether the cohort’s expressed stances, taken together, lean more positive or more negative within that dimension. These two numbers separate ‘how much evidence is present’ (activation) from ‘which way the cohort leans’ (orientation), which prevents a common interpretive failure in audience analytics where weak evidence and strong polarity are conflated.

Film-level reporting. When $C = \mathcal{R}_f$, CineFlux reports film-level profiles consisting of: (i) per-variable mean activation and mean signed orientation, and (ii) dimension-level aggregated activation and aggregated signed orientation—this combination is deliberate. Dimension-level scores support rapid comparison across films and countries; per-variable means provide the explanation layer that makes those comparisons interpretable and audit-ready.

Group-conditioned reporting (public vs segmented). CineFlux applies the same aggregation procedure to group-conditioned cohorts, for example $C_{f,public}$ (public reviews of film f) and C_{f,a_i} (reviews of f produced by segmented audience a_i). Because the scoring protocol is identical, CineFlux can compute divergence measures directly: the tool can report where a segment differs from the public baseline in activation (what the segment attends to) and in signed orientation (how the segment evaluates it). This supports the deliverable’s central

stakeholder use-case: diagnosing audience-film fit, identifying potential reception risks, and distinguishing ‘general audience patterns’ from segment-specific responses.

Traceability and reproducibility. All aggregated outputs remain traceable to the review-level canonical objects and their extractive evidence spans. The aggregation stage is therefore not a black box: it is a deterministic summary over auditable inputs, governed by pipeline parameters (including marker weights) stored alongside the schema version. This allows reviewers and project partners to reproduce film- and cohort-level scores exactly, and to audit unexpected outcomes by drilling down from an aggregate score to the variables, then to the underlying evidence spans.

Note. Formal math notation and definitions are available in Supplementary Information SI WP73-C-01.

7.4.5 Activation and signed orientation at cohort level

Mean signed orientation

Two clarifications matter for interpretation and for how the CineFlux UI simplifies the results.

1. $\bar{\alpha}_{c,y} \approx 0$ **means the variable is not meaningfully active**, regardless of $\bar{\sigma}_{c,y}$

If there is little or no evidence for, y , across the cohort, any apparent leaning is not decision-relevant. This is why the discretized view should treat activation as the first gate: **orientation is only interpreted once activation is above an activation threshold.**

2. $\bar{\sigma}_{c,y} \approx 0$ **does not imply ‘no stance’.**

A cohort can be highly polarized (many positive and many negative stances) and still yield $\bar{\sigma}_{c,y} \approx 0$ due to cancellation. That indicates **no net direction**, not absence of value-laden reception.

If stakeholders need a measure of “how much directional stance exists” irrespective of sign, CineFlux can report an additional magnitude statistic, for example:

$$M_{C,y} = \frac{1}{n_C} \sum_{r \in C} |\sigma_{r,y}|$$

(or equivalently: a mean of $\alpha_{r,y}$ restricted to reviews with directional stances). This separates **polarization/intensity** from **net leaning**.

Finally, because, α , and, σ , are derived from the canonical markers via weights, the activation threshold used for discretization (e.g., $\bar{\alpha} = 0.5$ as a practical ‘active vs inactive’ boundary) must be stated as a **pipeline choice**: it is meaningful because it is applied consistently under a fixed scoring configuration. The formal definitions, weight dependence, and aggregation equations are specified in Supplementary Information SI WP73-C-01.

7.4.6 Illustrative example

Assume one variable $y = \text{hedonic_humour_amusement}$, and a small cohort, C , of five reviews of the same film. Each review yields (i) trigger t , (ii) appraisal a , and (iii) stance label s . CineFlux then computes:

Activation $\alpha_{r,y}$, as a weighted evidence score (example weights):

- $w_t = 0.2$ for trigger,
- $w_a = 0.4$, for appraisal, and
- $w_s = 0.4$, for directional stance (only when stance is positive/negative).

Signed orientation $\sigma_{r,y}$ as $\sigma_{r,y} = \alpha_{r,y} o_{r,y}$, where $o_{r,y} \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$ is the mapping of stance label (qualitative) to stance sign, i.e., +1 positive; -1 negative, and 0 for neutral, unclear, and None. See Supplementary Information SI WP73-C-01.

Review	What reviewer says	Trigger	Appraisal	Stance	$\alpha_{r,y}$	$\sigma_{r,y}$
R1	"A blast. So much fun."	1	1	Pos	1.0	+1.0
R2	"Fun in places, mostly tedious."	1	1	Neg	1.0	-1.0
R3	"Light entertainment."	1	0	Neu	0.2	0
R4	<< plot summary >>	0	0	None	0	0
R5	"Entertaning enough"	1	1	Pos	1	+1.0

Assuming—for this example—that we remain within the scope of the **hedonic pathway** in the **motivational orientation** (MO) dimension, and denote it by, \mathbf{H} , then to compute, $\alpha_{r,H}$, (activation vector), and, $\sigma_{r,H}$, (signed orientation vector), we would need to compute the variable activations and signed orientations for the remaining three variables, $\mathbf{y} \in H$, that is thrill-arousal, comfort-mood-regulation and hedonic-generic.

We can, however, illustrate the aggregated cohort value for our chosen variable,

$\mathbf{y} = \text{hedonic_humour_amusement}$

The mean gives the mean activation for the cohort:

$$\bar{\alpha}_{c,y} = \frac{1}{5} (1.0 + 1.0 + 0.2 + 0 + 1.0) = \frac{3.2}{5} = 0.64$$

Mean signed orientation for the cohort:

$$\bar{\sigma}_{c,y} = \frac{1}{5} (+1.0 - 1.0 + 0 + 0 + 1.0) = \frac{1.0}{5} = 0.20$$

How to interpret the pair $\bar{\alpha}_{c,y} = 0.64$, $\bar{\sigma}_{c,y} = 0.2$?

The mean cohort activation, $\bar{\alpha}_{c,y} = 0.64$, means the reviews in, \mathcal{C} , speak about humour-amusement fairly often, resulting in moderate-to-strong evidence overall. On the other hand, the mean signed orientation $\bar{\sigma}_{c,y} = 0.2$, captures that, when reviewers do take a directional stance, the net lean is mildly positive (positive stance outweighs negative, but not overwhelmingly)

8 The CineFlux tool

8.1 Purpose and positioning

The CineFlux MVP⁴ is not a film analytics dashboard in the quantitative/predictive sense. It is a stakeholder-facing decision instrument that makes audience reception legible at the level of meaning, value, and motivation—using explicit theory-grounded constructs rather than opaque sentiment or generic engagement metrics. The visible value is the tool’s ability to provide nuanced explanations of past-trend audiovisual audience reception; the enabling innovation is twofold: (a) the underlying canonical inference model, which converts unstructured review text into auditable markers (trigger → appraisal expression → stance) that can be aggregated safely into variable- and dimension-level indicators (see §7.3 and §7.4), and (b) the tool’s support for using audience-segment, and (non-segmented) public review data (see §6).

⁴ The deliverable’s repository is located at <https://github.com/AISIC-Lab/crescine-cineflux>

The CineFlux MVP is located at <https://www.crescine.eu/cineflux>

The key user-facing goal is to allow a funding or policy stakeholder to see, at a glance, (i) what kinds of reception patterns exist for a film (or film set), (ii) how a target segment diverges from a public baseline, and (iii) what that divergence implies for intercultural circulation and audience-development interventions. This is aligned with European cultural priorities because it supports evidence-based decisions about diversity in creation and distribution. More concretely, funding decisions can be supported by **data-driven explanations of past trends** on what audiovisual works resonated with which publics, where meaning ‘failed to travel’, and what is realistically adjustable (contextualization, framing, targeting, mediation) without collapsing into a profit/predictive optimization logic. Note that in this context, explanations are not open, but instead are bounded by the scope of the CineFlux model.

8.1.1 The CineFlux operational resources

Individual **film reviews** (public, or segmented) are the **units of analysis** in CineFlux. For each review, the backend produces a structured reception fingerprint derived from the model’s dimensions and variable-level outputs, all expressed within the same trigger → appraisal → stance framework (see §7.2). On the other hand, a **review cohort** is the primary focus of the user. A review cohort will typically result from a query that includes the producer country and additional attributes, such as genre, director, and others. A well-formed query will yield a cohort that always includes public reviews and, where available, segmented reviews.

8.1.2 A minimalistic ‘story spine’

The system’s backend and frontend were designed to tell one coherent story, in one screen, with three layers of interpretation:

Layer 1 → Overview: What does the landscape of reception look like? This presents the distribution of reception patterns: clusters, spread, and disagreement.

Layer 2 → Contrast: How do target segments diverge from the public baseline? This makes differences explicit and quantified rather than anecdotal.

Layer 3 → Consequence: What does this imply for funding and circulation? This translates divergence into stakeholder-relevant language: opportunities, risks, and plausible intervention levers.

This structure is deliberately minimal. It avoids feature sprawl and keeps the experience anchored in three questions that matter to a funder: ‘What is happening?’, ‘For whom?’, and ‘So what?’

8.1.3 The centrepiece: the reception map

The central system affordance that enables the user to map the explanatory backbone of audience reception is a **two-dimensional projection** (see SI WP73-C-01 §2 for details) of the reviews in the chosen cohort—as represented by the CineFlux internal model—where each review exists in the high-dimensional space of *dimensions* → *variables* → *markers*. Reviews are visualized as circles, with properties such as colour and shape encoding interpretable information. The map is not about ‘aesthetics’; it is a compact representation of distances in reception space. We rely on appropriate dimensionality-reduction methods (e.g., MDS/UMAP) for the two-dimensional projection. The key goal of the projection is to **preserve distance relationships** that naturally exist in the original space. This way, nearby circles (reviews) correspond to similar reception fingerprints. Visual proximity is thus directly interpretable. From the user’s perspective, this translates into observing, for example, that ‘these reviews are similar in what they pick up and how the reviewers evaluate them’.

Encodings. For each review circle, (a) **colour** encodes the audience source: a public baseline versus one or more segmented audiences (focus-group-derived); (b) **size** encodes user rating so the stakeholder can see whether a cluster corresponds to uniformly high, low, or

mixed ratings; (c) **stroke** encodes a compressed view of the review's stance profile across all activated variables in the audience model. For each review, CineFlux first identifies which MF/MO variables are both activated and carry a directional stance (positive or negative). It then measures the balance of signed 'stance mass' over those variables: if most activated variables lean to positive, the net valence is positive; if most lean negative, the net valence is negative; if positives and negatives have around the same 'mass', they cancel each other out, and the net valence is close to zero. Stroke colour represents this net valence (e.g. greenish hues for net-positive, reddish hues for net-negative, neutral grey when the stance pattern is mixed or weak), while stroke width increases with stance strength (how many variables are involved and how confidently they lean in one direction). For an audience expert, the abstraction represents, at a glance, whether a review is largely endorsing or rejecting the morally and motivationally salient aspects it engages with, and how coherent that stance is across dimensions. It does not represent the morality of the film itself, general like/dislike sentiment, or detailed per-variable content; rather, it is a compact visual summary of how aligned or conflicted the review's evaluative language is within the specific MF/MO framework.

Semantic anchors. To prevent the map from looking like an abstract scatterplot, the CineFlux design allows placing faint 'anchor labels' for selected variables. Operationally, this is implemented as a tooltip on the interface. When the user hovers (and pauses momentarily) over reviews, the tooltip shows key review characterization and audience-model data. This gives stakeholders an immediate semantic reading of regions of the map: where the 'care/harm' cluster sits, where 'authority' reactions concentrate, where 'hedonic enjoyment' dominates, and where 'eudaimonic reflection' appears.

Notes: (1) While we collected a large corpus and used carefully selected samples to validate the model and pipeline, the MVP demonstrates the interface and decision logic on a limited number of films due to computational cost, not conceptual or methodological limitations; (2) The projection is an interpretive aid, not an analytical result in itself; all the reception

indicators shown elsewhere in the interface are computed in the original high-dimensional reception space.

8.1.4 Left panel: query and comparison controls

The left panel exists to define the analysis run in terms stakeholders understand. It should remain short and stable:

Film selection and scope. A simple **query selector** lets users select the production country, genre, and release-year range to define a review cohort. This selection instantiates a scrollable list of titles. The user then selects the films to be added to the final cohort for analysis. While the definition of cohorts is limited to exploring the reception map of one film at a time in the MVP, the underlying design allows for adding the multi-film cohort analysis feature in future versions. The CineFlux MVP was designed to enable stakeholders to run the same analysis protocol across individual titles in a cohort of interest and compare results consistently.

Audience mode. A **three-way selector** lets the user choose between seeing public reviews only, segmented only, or combined (public and segments) when segmented data is available. Combined mode is the default for policy use because it makes divergence visible. When combined, circle colours distinguish public and segmented reviews. In the MVP, this feature was implemented for a single segmented audience, but the underlying design allows for seamless multi-segment feature implementation in future versions.

Dimension focus. The MVP was designed to allow users to choose whether to view reception data for the moral foundations, motivational orientation, or both. This does not alter the UI structure; it alters the underlying representation and the semantic anchors displayed. Stakeholders should never feel they have entered a different tool. The MVP allows only the combined option.

8.1.5 *Right panel: the decision lens*

The right panel consolidates the information encoded in the reception map into decision-oriented summaries. Its function is not to introduce new analytics, but to stabilize the reception map interpretation by helping stakeholders read structure, divergence, and evidential strength in ways that are grounded in the CineFlux model and traceable to review language. The panel is organized into three stacked blocks, each corresponding to one layer of the CineFlux ‘story backbone’: overview, contrast, and consequence.

Block A. Reception profile overview

Block A provides a compact overview of how different audience sources engage with the explanatory variables in the CineFlux model. For each available source (public baseline and any segmented cohort), the panel displays three small profile summaries corresponding to:

Moral Foundations (MF), Motivational Orientation (hedonic pathway), and Motivational Orientation (eudaimonic pathway). Each profile summarizes, per variable, two observable properties derived from the review annotations, (a) **activation** and (b) **signed orientation** (see §7.4).

Visually, these are rendered as compact, zero-centred sparkline views. For each variable, positive-stance activation is drawn above the reference line, negative-stance activation below it. Colour encodes orientation (e.g. blue for net-positive, red for net-negative), while proximity to the zero line indicates weak or mixed uptake. Hover interaction reveals the variable name and supporting evidence counts. The purpose of Block A is descriptive rather than comparative: it allows the stakeholder to see *what kinds of moral and motivational constructs are active* in each audience source, and whether they are predominantly endorsed, rejected, or internally conflicted. This block answers the question: **‘What does reception look like for this audience?’**

Block B. Segment divergence indicators

Block B makes audience differences explicit by showing where a segmented audience diverges most strongly from the public baseline. For each variable, divergence is computed as the difference in activation rates between sources, separately for positive and negative stance.

In practice, this yields simple, interpretable shifts. A variable may be more positively activated in the segment than in the public baseline, more negatively activated, or both. These differences are displayed as small, stable bar indicators centred on zero, with direction and magnitude directly interpretable as ‘more’ or ‘less’ engagement relative to the public baseline. This block answers the question: **‘Where, specifically, does this audience differ from the public?’**. This block is only shown when the current reception map contains at least one segmented cohort.

Block C. Evidence coverage and interpretive reliability

Block C provides a minimal but critical reliability lens. Rather than reporting abstract model accuracy, it exposes observable properties of the underlying evidence that condition interpretation. The block reports: (a) **Coverage**: how frequently each dimension is activated in the current cohort; (b) **Balance checks**: whether positive and negative stances are both present or heavily skewed; (c) **Sparsity flags**: alerts when a dimension or variable is weakly supported for a given film or audience source. These indicators are designed to sit in the stakeholder’s line of sight, preventing over-interpretation of thin or uneven evidence. They reinforce the CineFlux design principle that insights are *bounded by what is actually said in the data*. This block answers the question: **‘How much confidence should I place in what I am seeing?’**

Relationship to the reception map

The right panel does not duplicate the map; it *constrains its reading*. Block A summarizes the internal structure visible in clusters and spreads. Block B explains which variables are

responsible for separations between sources. Block C qualifies both with evidence strength. Together, the panel translates spatial intuition into grounded, inspectable claims suitable for funding, policy, and circulation discussions.

Note. The backend architecture of CineFlux supports all computations described above. In the MVP, the right panel focuses on a stable subset of these summaries to ensure robustness and clarity; additional refinements are foreseen for later iterations.

Note. In the MVP, the right panel prioritizes a small, stable subset of summaries that can be computed robustly from activation and stance data; more advanced consolidation views are specified at design level.

8.1.6 CineFlux support for funding and policy decisions

This UX is intentionally tuned to three decision tasks that occur in film alignment and circulation contexts.

First, diagnosing interpretive fit and friction. A stakeholder assesses whether a film’s reception landscape is coherent (tight clusters) or fractured (dispersed or loose clusters), and whether the fractures align with audience segments. This supports decisions about whether a film is likely to circulate smoothly, require mediation, or remain niche.

Second, making segment divergence operational. The tool expresses divergence as a patterned shift in moral/motivational reception, not as a vague ‘this audience likes it’. This is the essential move from marketing segmentation to cultural circulation analysis. Stakeholders can identify which aspects of meaning travel across publics, and which do not.

Third, linking divergence to realistic interventions. Because the backend model separates presence, appraisal, and stance, and keeps scope disciplined, stakeholders can reason about interventions that are plausible and ethically defensible. If a segment registers the story-world moral logic but appraises it negatively, that suggests a different intervention than if the logic is not registered at all. The tool is designed to surface that distinction directly.

8.1.7 The CineFlux innovation

Most audience analytics systems are behaviour-centric (views, completion, clicks) or sentiment-centric (positive/negative tone). CineFlux is reception-centric in a precise, auditable sense: it instruments constructs that matter for public value–moral interpretation and motivational engagement—and makes them inspectable at scale.

The innovation is not simply ‘using an LLM’. It is the coupling of (i) canonical, theory-aligned inference that externalizes its grounds, with (ii) a minimal interface that preserves auditability while making divergence legible to non-technical stakeholders. This combination is what allows the tool to support European priorities: evidence-based decisions for diversity, intercultural exchange, and public-value circulation—without replacing human judgement, and without reducing culture to engagement optimization.

In short, the backend model makes the UX possible; the UX is where stakeholders receive value. The MVP is therefore designed as a disciplined ‘decision lens’: one screen, three layers (overview, contrast, consequence), and every claim traceable to evidence.

9 Conclusions and future work

CineFlux was developed to address a concrete gap in current audience-intelligence practice for small European film markets. Existing tools largely quantify attention—views, ratings, completion rates—while offering little insight into why particular audiences respond as they do,

or how those responses diverge across publics and strategically important segments. **The CineFlux MVP demonstrates that it is now feasible to model audience reception in a way that is both computationally powerful and conceptually interpretable, using language as evidence and theory as structure** rather than relying on opaque metrics alone.

The work reported in this deliverable makes three main contributions. First, it defines a theory-grounded audience model centred on two well-established psychological dimensions: Moral Foundations and Motivational Orientation. These dimensions are reformulated as reception variables that can be inferred from text using a canonical Trigger → Appraisal expression → Stance structure, preserving a close link between psychological constructs and observable review language. Second, it implements an evidence-constrained LLM annotation pipeline that externalizes its own reasoning. Every inferred marker is backed by an extractive quote and a minimal justification, stored in a reproducible JSON schema that allows downstream scoring to remain transparent and auditable. Third, it delivers a dashboard MVP that renders these abstractions usable for decision-makers: reviews are positioned in a common 2D space, cohorts can be contrasted within the same coordinate system, and all visual cues are traceable back to concrete textual evidence.

Beyond the tool itself, CineFlux contributes a methodological template for combining public reviews with purpose-designed segmented audience data. Public Letterboxd reviews for a curated corpus of Portuguese and Danish films provide a broad baseline of reception; synchronous digital focus groups supply a contrasted, demographically defined segment whose discourse is harmonized into review-like units under a strict no-addition/no-deletion protocol. Both sources are processed through the same annotation and scoring pipeline, enabling comparison of film- and cohort-level profiles without sacrificing traceability. This reframes ‘persona’ not as a static a priori ideal type, but as a relational profile inferred from observed discourse—this way, stakeholders can see how reception for a given film shifts between the public baseline and targeted segments.

9.1 Limitations and risks

The CineFlux MVP is deliberately scoped and should be read as a proof of concept rather than a finished product. Empirically, it is restricted to synthetic data, to films produced in two countries (Portugal and Denmark) and to a single segmented cohort (Portuguese students aged 18–24) discussing one focal film title. The current corpus is sufficient to demonstrate the model’s use and innovation on a dashboard, but it does not yet support claims about all small European markets or about the full diversity of audience segments relevant to policy and industry decision-making. Further work is needed to extend both film coverage and the range of segmented cohorts, including older age groups, international audiences and professional stakeholders.

At the tooling level, the cohort query builder in the MVP is limited to a small set of metadata fields—production country, genre and release year. This is adequate for the present corpus, but many practical use cases require finer-grained control, for example filtering by director, producers, festival circuit, funding source, or WP3-style market clusters and value-chain indicators. The current design is compatible with these extensions, but they are not yet implemented.

The most significant long-term risk concerns dependence on a commercial LLM for annotation. For the MVP, we prioritized reliability and instruction-following accuracy, which currently favour proprietary models that have undergone extensive reinforcement learning from human feedback. However, this reliance is not sustainable in the long term and is not fully aligned with European commitments to openness, sovereignty and data-protection-aware infrastructure. Preliminary tests with a strong open model (Llama 3 70B instruct) showed that, without equivalent instruction-tuning and safety alignment, it does not yet provide the level of controllability required by our canonical prompting protocol. This creates a technical and governance risk that must be addressed in future iterations.

Finally, there are methodological limitations intrinsic to the present focus. The model currently operationalizes only two of the five dimensions in the broader CineFlux framework, and all inference is performed on text written in or translated into a small set of languages. While cross-lingual consistency has been encouraged through prompt design and conservative saturation procedures, it has not yet been systematically validated. Moreover, although the annotation pipeline is explicitly auditable, its quantitative properties (e.g. stability under re-runs, sensitivity to prompt variants, and alignment with human annotations) merit further formal validation beyond the initial reliability checks conducted for this MVP.

A final clarification concerns the interpretation of moral variables in CineFlux. The Moral Foundations dimension is used strictly as a framework for analysing *reception*, not for profiling individuals or inferring stable moral identities. All moral signals captured by the system are grounded in what reviewers explicitly say about the film’s narrative world—its characters, actions, themes, and implied values—and how they evaluate those elements. CineFlux does not model who audience members “are” morally; it models how specific works are *received and discussed* in moral terms by different publics. This distinction is central to the system’s design and ethical positioning. By treating moral foundations as properties of discourse and interpretation rather than of persons, CineFlux aligns with established reception theory, avoids individual-level moral attribution, and remains compatible with European principles of data protection, accountability, and responsible use of AI in cultural analysis.

9.2 Future development and integration

Future work on CineFlux will proceed along three intertwined tracks: theoretical extension, data and infrastructure scaling, and user-centred productization. On the theoretical side, the immediate priority is to extend the operationalized model beyond Moral Foundations and Motivational Orientation. The full CineFlux framework includes additional dimensions capturing ideological selectivity, cultural positioning and cognitive-style differences in reception. Each

dimension can be instantiated under the same canonical Trigger → Appraisal → Stance architecture, with its own discriminant logic and stance rules. As new dimensions are added, the combined activation space will become richer, allowing more nuanced reception profiles without changing the underlying scoring or visualization pipeline.

On the data and infrastructure side, CineFlux should be scaled to more films, more countries and more audience segments. This includes expanding the public-review corpus to cover additional small European markets and genres, integrating further upstream descriptors from WP2 and WP3 (for example, production attributes, market clusters and policy-toolkit indicators), and conducting new rounds of digital focus groups with strategically selected cohorts in multiple countries. The same backend JSON schema can be reused across these extensions, ensuring that additional data remains interoperable with the existing corpus. Parallel work is needed to reduce dependence on proprietary LLMs: this may involve collaboration with open-source model developers, exploring lightweight instruction-tuning on open models, or deploying hybrid architectures where open models handle less sensitive tasks while commercial models are reserved for high-precision annotation under strict governance rules.

On the productization side, the MVP points towards a more interactive and socially embedded CineFlux ecosystem. One line of development is to turn the segmented focus-group infrastructure into an open, research-oriented CineFlux chat platform where participants can discuss films under informed consent, with audience-characterization data collected in a privacy-preserving way and mapped directly into the CineFlux model space. Another is to enrich the dashboard with intelligent conversational capabilities: by leveraging the embeddings and evidence spans already stored in the backend, a user could interrogate specific regions of the reception map, ask ‘why’ a segment diverges from the public baseline, or request concrete quotes exemplifying a pattern, all within a controlled, auditable interface.

9.3 Closing remarks

CineFlux does not replace traditional qualitative audience research or existing quantitative metrics; it complements them. It offers a middle layer between individual close reading and high-level counts: a structured, interpretable representation of how different audiences talk about films along moral and motivational dimensions, with every abstraction traceable back to language. In doing so, CineFlux provides funders, policymakers and industry stakeholders with a new way of reasoning about audiences in small European markets, one that is sensitive to meaning and value rather than only to volume and reach.

The present MVP is intentionally modest in empirical scope, but ambitious in methodological and infrastructural terms. It establishes a reusable pipeline—from corpus construction, through theory-aligned LLM annotation, to evidence-backed visualisation—that can be extended across countries, audience segments and theoretical dimensions. As such, it constitutes a foundation on which future CRESCINE work and external partners can build more comprehensive, ethically grounded audience-intelligence systems for European cinema.

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